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Moog project The manual

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Part I

Moog usage

Chapter 1

Theory

1.1 Introduction

The **Moog 6DOF2000E** is a six-degrees-of-freedom platform that can carry a weight of about one metric ton¹. This manual describes a software package that I developed during the second half of 2019 to permit the control of the platform from a high level of abstraction.

¹Apparently, Moog is not producing this model anymore: it has been substituted by model **MB-E-6DOF/12**. I could not find anywhere what the differences between the two models actually are.

1.2 The platform

1.2.1 Geometry

Figure 1.1: The platform

The platform is constituted by two irregular hexagonal bases (with three longer sides and three shorter ones) connected via six actuators, as illustrated in Fig. 1.1. Five lengths completely describe the geometric model:

Tag	Description	Constant	Length (m)
L1	The longer side of the lower hexagon	LONG_SIDE_LOWER	1.262
L2	The shorter side of the lower hexagon	SHORT_SIDE	0.2031
U1	The longer side of the upper hexagon	LONG_SIDE_UPPER	0.8884
U2	The shorter side of the upper hexagon	SHORT_SIDE	0.2031
A	The attenuator length	-	Variable

The hexagon values are defined as constants of class `Platf`, in source file `scripts/moo.rb`. These values are directly derived from the blueprints obtained from Moog, that can be found in the `docs` directory (`blueprint.pdf`).

The actuators

The actuators are the moving parts of the platform. The Moog documentation provide a minimum and a maximum length for them, that it is possible to ask them to adopt. These measurements do *not* coincide with the measurement distance between the two connected joints. In my code, I define a further constant to contain the measured fixed length to be added to the actuator length communicated to the platform in order to obtain the measured length.

Measurement	Value (m)	Constant
Minimum	0.03048	MOO_ACTU_MIN
Maximum	0.297	MOO_ACTU_MAX
Fixed	0.70865	MOO_ACTU_FIXED

The fixed value has been extrapolated from measurements included in the blueprints provided by Moog.

The Moog manual provided a maximum extension value of 0.30988. This value, when submitted to the platform, caused it to enter a **fault state**. I experimentally reduced the maximum value to the one shown above, which appears to be safe.

1.2.2 Degree-of-freedom values

The position of the upper hexagon of the platform with regards to the lower hexagon can be specified in two ways:

- with the length of each of the six actuators, as described above.
- By passing three linear and three angular values, that directly fix each of the six degrees of freedom of the device.

Moog associates names to the six degrees of freedom, as shown in Fig. 1.1. Linear values are specified in **metres**, and angular values are specified in **radians**. Positive and negative directions for each are shown in the figure.

It then defines, for the messages it expects as input and those it agenerates as output, a specific order for the six values:

1. ROLL (angular)
2. PITCH (angular)
3. heave (linear)
4. surge (linear)
5. YAW (angular)
6. lateral (linear)

This is the order in which degree-of-freedom values are expected to be received by the protocol that has been designed for this project, and in which values will be written in result files.

1.2.3 The model

Using these measurements, a software model of the platform can be created, and with its aid one can easily convert from the six degree-of-freedom values to the six actuator values. This operation is called *inverse kinematics*.

The reverse operation, called *forward kinematics*, is more difficult, and has no known direct solution. This computation is generally performed by progressive approximation.

I decided to limit my code to inverse kinematics: motion sequences are to be specified with degree-of-freedom values, and it is these values that are interpolated when performing motions with given durations.

The software operating on the platform is able to perform forward kinematics: it can receive either DoF values or actuator lengths as inputs, but (in the current configuration) it returns the current DoF values in its status messages.

It would be interesting if Moog could share technical details about how they implemented the two operations, and which lengths they use.

1.3 Motion profiles

The platform moves between sets of degree-of-freedom values. Interpolation between the sets along time can be performed using several methods.

1.3.1 Linear interpolation

Figure 1.2: Velocity and acceleration in linear interpolation

Linear interpolation is the simplest method to calculate intermediate values between two known values associated to moments in time. If you move linearly, your speed will be constant, and your acceleration will be zero. In figure 1.2, an object moves, say, five meters in five seconds. The speed is constant at $1m/s$.

It is to be kept in mind that, when beginning and ending a motion with linear interpolation, two moments with theoretically infinite acceleration take place. In practice, the Moog platform will introduce a dampening effect, but a strong irregularity will be perceived.

1.3.2 Sinewave interpolation

Figure 1.3: Velocity and acceleration in sinewave interpolation

With sinewave interpolation, the factor to obtain intermediate values is obtained by considering the value of the sine function mapped to the range between $-\pi/2$ and $\pi/2$. From figure 1.3, it can be seen that velocity starts at zero, but with a slope, and acceleration begins at a value of $1m/s^2$, and is at $-1m/s^2$ at the end of the motion. Again, these are theoretical values, because, again, the platform will add a dampening effect, but an irregularity in the motion will be perceived, although much less intense compared to linear interpolation.

1.3.3 De Casteljau interpolation

Figure 1.4: Velocity and acceleration in De Casteljau interpolation

I implemented an interpolation mechanism following *De Casteljau's* algorithm². By selecting these control points:
0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, 1.0, 1.0

the resulting interpolation has a second derivative of zero at beginning and end, which ensures that the motion begins smoothly (see Figure 1.4).

²see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/De_Casteljau's_algorithm

1.3.4 Interpolation by imposing a sinewave shape to the acceleration profile

Figure 1.5: Position, velocity and acceleration with sinewave acceleration profile

The software that was provided by Moog to operate the platform uses an interpolation method that imposes a sinewave shape to the *acceleration* profile, and integrates from it the speed and eventually the interpolation value at a given time.

Five variables, added to the fact of imposing a sinewave profile to the acceleration, define the procedure:

- The maximum **linear acceleration**.
- The **linear displacement**.
- The maximum **angular acceleration**.
- The **angular displacement**.
- The **time** that the displacement will take.

The user must specify **three** of the above variables, and the two remaining ones will be computed from the provided values.

Among the user-specified variables, at least **one linear** and **one angular** value must be specified.

The most common way that the Institute normally uses this feature that of specifying a maximum speed and a displacement, either linear or angular, often having no motion of the other type, and let the system define the time of the motion.

I implemented the same functionality for the *long sequence* session type (see P.20), where all eight possible combinations of input values can be specified. You can learn the details about the implementation by reading the section about command LONG_SEQ_STEP_SINEACC, on P. 47. The example in Fig. 1.5 shows the case where

a **linear displacement** of $5m$, an angular displacement of zero, and a time of $5s$ were set as preconditions. The resulting maximum angular acceleration is of course zero, while the maximum linear acceleration is, as returned by the algorithm, of $1.2566m/s^2$.

Note that the De Casteljau interpolation described above obtains a lower maximum value of acceleration, while maintaining the precondition of having an acceleration of zero both at the beginning and at the end of the displacement.

1.3.5 Damped harmonic oscillator interpolation

Figure 1.6: Damped harmonic oscillation

The interpolator described in this section has the task of mimicking the behaviour of a damped spring-like oscillator, applying the calculated behaviour to the motion of the platform.

The motion is supposed to overshoot the intended destination, later rebounding and damping its oscillation until the destination is reached.

In Fig. 1.6 you can see an example of applying damped harmonic oscillator interpolation to the movement from 1 to 0. These parameters define the system:

- The **mass** of the oscillating object.
- The **elasticity constant** of the spring.
- The **dampening factor**.
- The maximum **duration time**.
- The low **energy level** threshold to consider the motion as completed.

The maximum length is an indicator. The motion will stop as soon as the energy level of the oscillator drops below the passed.

I implemented this functionality for the *long sequence* session type (see P.20). You will have the possibility of using command LONG_SEQ_STEP_DAMPEDOSC to define a step using the damped harmonic oscillator interpolation for *all but the first* steps you define. You can learn the details about the implementation by reading the section about command LONG_SEQ_STEP_DAMPEDOSC, on P. 48.

Important tip: It is not easy to obtain the right values for a valid motion range. The overshoot effect makes the platform move more than required, and it is easy to violate either the actuator length limits or those of speed.

The graph in Fig. 1.6 was generated with these values:

- Mass: 1.1
- Spring constant: 5.5
- Damping factor: 0.7

I applied these parameters to a damped-oscillation step that is moving the platform from -4° to 4° on the yaw axis. The motion lasted 13.45s.

In Fig. 1.7 you can see the end effect on the yaw asset of the platform. The step lasts from about nine and a half seconds and is concluded at just over 23 seconds.

Figure 1.7: Damped harmonic oscillation in practice

Chapter 2

Practice

2.1 Sessions

The code that has been written for this project executes the following tasks:

- It connects to the Moog platform's black box via UDP. The socket parameters that my code uses are, as far as I know, immutable unless black box runtime options are changed. They are as follows:
 - **Server address:** 192.168.1.12
 - **Server port:** 992
 - **Platform address:** 192.168.1.200
 - **Server port:** 991

The code must have *exclusive* access to the platform.

- It allows access to any one client, on a first-come, first-served basis, who will contact it by sending a login packet to an open UDP socket. The parameters of this socket are:
 - **Server address:** 192.168.1.201
 - **Server port:** 1860

This second address is configurable, according to usage needs. The chosen values make the server accessible by computers that will connect their ethernet cards by UTP wire to the switch that currently connects the Moog platform and the three computers running the legacy software.

Those computers will have to be manually configured so that their wired ethernet port is active and assigned to an address between 192.168.1.202/24 and 192.168.1.254/24.

The connection establishment procedure will be illustrated in detail later on in this document.

- It manages sessions, in which it translates the requirements of the connected clients to commands to send to the Moog platform, and it keeps the client informed in real time about the runtime state.
- It monitors the status of the platform and the requested actuator lengths in order to preventively validate the proposed platform behaviour.
- It collects run data for the sessions, and it eventually packages and delivers them to given `unibe` e-mail addresses.
- It updates the contents of a monitor screen, so that those who operate the experiments may keep the situation under visual control.
- It provides upon request the lists of past sessions for given days, and can generate and eventually deliver run data reports for each session.

2.1.1 Session types

Four session types are currently defined.

Immediate

This session type expects the client to send degree-of-freedom data that will be immediately submitted to the platform. For each requested step, the server will verify that the destination position is permissible given the platform geometry, and that the distance between the present and the requested position is lower than a provided maximum value for each of the 6 degree-of-freedom values.

Short sequence

This type of session permits to the client, once it has asked the platform to engage itself, to submit sequences of steps, each one to be performed within a given amount of time.

Each sequence will be initiated at the current platform position.

When a sequence has been received, it will be validated according to:

- **Validity of all positions of the proposed trajectory** which have to be within the reachable area of the platform.
- **Velocity of the motion of each attenuator for the proposed trajectory** at each time frame.

Validation takes place with the same time granularity that will be used to execute the sequence.

If the sequence has been validated, it will immediately begin executing.

This mode is applicable in situations where the client may modify the proposed platform trajectories in real time during session execution.

Long sequence

In this mode, a series of named sequences will be submitted to the system. The sequences will build up a library.

Subsequently, the platform will be engaged, and it will be possible to execute each of the sequences in any order and as often as needed.

In this case, the first position of the sequence is considered as the start point. Sequence invocation will be done in two steps:

- First, the platform will be positioned to the start point. both the intermediate positions and the speeds of this displacement will be verified before it is executed.
- Once the start position is reached, the sequence can be performed.

Sequences are validated beforehand, in the same way as described above for short sequences¹. Only the displacement to reach the start point will need to be verified in real time.

Joystick

If this session type is required, the server will configure itself so that the joystick that is currently connected to it will be able to control the actual position of the platform.

¹There are no limits imposed on the lengths of sequences, and it will certainly be possible to define *short* sequences that are longer than given *long* sequences. I gave these names to the two sequence types because, when planning possible behaviour, I thought that sequences that would be provided live while the platform is engaged would be in general shorter than fixed sequences arranged in named catalogs.

2.2 Threads

The server operates one main thread. Furthermore, the digital input-output pins reading mechanism and the joystick code make use of a thread each.

2.2.1 Main thread

The main thread manages the execution of single actions (reaching a specific location in a given time interval) It performs the following tasks:

- If an action is underway:
 - It calculates the interpolated values for the current motion at the current time.
 - It produces the current requested actuator lengths, and verifies that they are legal.
 - If the step is valid, it updates the **current official DoF values** that will be accessed by the *low-level* thread.
 - If the action has finished, or some error was raised, the action is canceled.
 - If the motion is valid, it saves its destination as last good position (both in DoF and in actuator lengths).
 - It saves the requested motion data to the related session log file.
- It collects eventual platform response messages that have been received by the socket.
- It saves these messages to the related session log file.
- If the platform is in fault mode, a reset of the platform is initiated.
- After a valid platform message has been received, it makes sure that one packet is sent to the platform, with the current situation.

At beginning, I had thought to set up a separate thread that would be responsible of keeping a precise sending rate. I often had occurrences of perceivable irregular motion by the platform, that after much effort were related to the interference of the server's and platform computer's message sending rates (the second one being quite irregular). The problem was solved by making sure that the server would keep its message sending in sync with the platform's.

2.3 Server on-off procedure

The server machine is based on a Linux distribution called Devuan². This distribution has the advantage of not being (necessarily) dependent on a package called `systemd`, which I prefer not to be dealing with.

I started with a simple installation from an installation disk for release ASCII. I then switched to the so-called unstable release (`ceres`, in order to have a more recent GCC) and removed a few packages in order to:

- Disable per-user network configuration (network is configured by a simple script at boot)
- Disable X session manager (X is started, in two possible ways, from `/etc/inittab`).

In its current situation, in normal usage, it is sufficient to boot the machine, after having connected to it two network cables. The screen should look similar to what is seen in Fig. 2.1.

²<https://devuan.org>

Figure 2.1: Screenshot (idle)

The machine can be cleanly shut off by *briefly* pressing the power button.

2.4 Client connection procedure

The current setup requires that clients' ethernet ports be connected by UTP cable to the network switch that is present in the Moog room. The wired network interface should be configured to use a fixed address between 192.168.1.201 and 192.168.1.254, with a netmask of 255.255.255.0. The gateway should be set to 192.168.1.200, although no routing to the external world will take place.

Once the network of the client machine is correctly configured, the client will be able to reach the listening socket that the server has opened, on port 1860. Here is a snippet in Ruby that opens a local socket and connects it to the listening socket.

```
skt=UDPSocket::new('AF_INET')
skt.bind('0.0.0.0',0)
```

```
skt.connect('192.168.1.200', '1860')
```

2.4.1 Logging in

In order to begin a session, a login message (see 3.4.10) has to be sent to the listening socket.

2.5 Hardware input devices

The system permits, as soon as a session has been started, to start a thread that manages one or more hardware devices that generate input. A generic mechanism has been devised, that permits:

- the saving of device raw data in session result directories, and its post-production tabulation in comma-separated files, and
- the communication of events to the client, via messages.

The session specifies which of the available devices need to be connected to.

Fig. 2.2 contains information about the devices for whom support is currently provided.

Tag	Description	Saved data	Returned events
gamepad	A controller for the Sony Playstation game console, connected via a <i>GreenAsia MaxFire Blaze2</i> USB adapter.	Usage data from buttons and joysticks present on the device. The condition of all buttons is reported in the post-production situation file.	Pressure and release of the requested subset of the available buttons.
spnav	A <i>3Dconnexion Space Navigator</i> 6-dof mouse ^a	Usage data from the device operation. The condition of the left and right buttons is reported in the post-production situation file.	Pressure and release of the requested subset of the available buttons.
xsense	An <i>Xsens MTx-series</i> motion tracker ^b	Gyroscope, magnetometer and gravitometer readings. These data are reported in the post-production situation file.	Nothing

^asee https://www.3dconnexion.com/spacemouse_compact/en/

^bThe producer can be found at <http://www.xsens.com>. This sensor series appears to have been discontinued. See http://phhum-a209-cp.unibe.ch:10012/M00/M00_Standalone/blob/master/docs/XsensMtx.pdf for programming details

Figure 2.2: Hardware input devices

The client can request access to any combination of the available hardware devices. The server will acknowledge the request only if **all** of the requested devices have been contacted. Otherwise, a `HW_INPUT_NAK` message will be returned, and the daemon will not be started.

See Sec. 3.9 for the details of the available protocol messages.

2.6 Stimuli

The software permits the generation of auditory and visual stimuli. A channel for each type needs to be opened with one message, then available stimuli can be selected with a message.

Channels have to be opened after a successful login, for any session type. Both video and audio channels are automatically closed when the session terminates.

2.6.1 Auditory stimuli

Every server is configured to make use of one output DSP channel to generate sounds.

The output audio channel to use is defined by two parameters: the progressive audio card ID and the progressive number of the output device to use.

On a Linux system, to learn what audio channels can be used, run this command:

```
aplay -l
```

The output may be similar to this:

```
**** List of PLAYBACK Hardware Devices ****
card 0: PCH [HDA Intel PCH], device 0: ALC221 Analog [ALC221 Analog]
  Subdevices: 1/1
  Subdevice #0: subdevice #0
card 1: NVidia [HDA NVidia], device 3: HDMI 0 [HDMI 0]
  Subdevices: 1/1
  Subdevice #0: subdevice #0
card 1: NVidia [HDA NVidia], device 7: HDMI 1 [HDMI 1]
  Subdevices: 1/1
  Subdevice #0: subdevice #0
```

From this output you learn that the computer has two output-capable audio boards. The first one is the audio chip on the motherboard, while the second one represents the audio playback capability offered by the video card, via the two provided outputs.

The system uses as default card **#0** and device **#0**. If another channel were to be used, it must be specified using two system variables:

- **AUDIO_BOARD**: assign to it the card value.
- **AUDIO_DSP**: assign to it the device value.

The system permits the simultaneous playback of up to 15 different sources. The number of sources (channels) available is specified when opening the subsystem (see Sec. 3.10.3). The sources of the various open channels will be added in order to compose the output stream.

Whenever the playback of a sample is required to a channel, that sample will **substitute** the sample being currently played. Samples on other channels will continue being played.

Files

The audio stimuli playback system is able to play back any file that is found in a directory that is found on the server machine:

```
/moog_base/audio_samples/
```

Files must be **in raw format**, 16-bit signed, stereo, sampled at 44,100 Hz. The file name must end with **.raw**. A Ruby script exists in the **scripts** subdirectory, called **audio_converter.rb**, which makes use of **Ffmpeg** to extract the audio from practically any existing media file, and generate a raw file ready for use by this system.

Messages

The messages to be used to handle the audio stimuli are described in Sect. 3.10.

2.6.2 Visual stimuli

Figure 2.3: The computer screen with one visual stimuli window open

This type of stimuli server starts an OpenGL engine that will manage zero or more video windows and/or the display surface of one HTC Vive visor.

Each display surface will show the contents of a virtual world, containing one or more surfaces, that may display a visual stimulus: a still-frame - an image or a uniform color, or a movie.

Surfaces can be flat rectangles (suited for displaying normal video content) or spherical (suited for displaying so-called 360-degree stills or movies³).

Fig. 2.3 indicates the components of a visual window shown on-screen:

Monitor screen In this case, for you it will mostly mean the screen on the table of the Moog lab, or the 3D screen displayed by the Vive visor.

Display surface The actual window that is created on the screen (more than one can be created), or the whole surface of the visor screen. In the example, a window has been created with these parameters:

```
0#0#1280#1024#0.43633
```

meaning that the window has to be displayed at an offset of 0,0 pixels from the top-left corner, must measure 1280x1024 pixels, and an angle of 25 degrees (0.43633 radians) must be used as field-of-view angle (vertical).

³For some info, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/360-degree_video

Virtual screen The rectangle in virtual space where the stimuli will be displayed. It has been created with this string:

```
F#0.0#0.0#-1500.0#0.0#1.5707963267948966#0.0#2000.0#2000.0
```

meaning that the flat virtual screen has been created at a position in space (x, y, z) of 0.0, 0.0, 1500.0 and with an orientation (yaw, pitch, roll) of 0.0, 1.5707963267948966, 0.0. The size of the screen is of 2000.0x2000.0.

Important tip: All screens are positioned in virtual space; sizes are expressed in millimeters. The location of the flat screens and of the center of the spherical screens is with relation to the position of the observer, hardcoded at [0, 0, 2500].

Important tip: Angles have to be expressed in radians. 1.5707963267948966 corresponds to 90° ($\pi/2$).

This rotation around the pitch axis is necessary because virtual screens, when they are created as 3D objects, are positioned flat on the ground.

Figure 2.4: A visual stimuli window with two spherical screens

Fig. 2.4 shows a visual window with two spherical screens. These screens are mostly used to display material shot from an omnidirectional camera.

These cameras are actually sets of multiple cameras with a large focal angle, positioned on a spherical surface. The various flat images are then stitched together to represent *the projection on a cylinder of what would be perceived by a spherical sensor positioned in the middle of the scene*. The cylinder is then cut at some point, and flattened. Fig. 2.5 shows an image of what such images look like.

The rightmost screen in Fig. 2.4 shows the example image displayed on *the exterior* of the screen. This is the most intuitive way to think about displaying an image from an omnidirectional camera, but it gives a *fish-eye-like* effect. The screen has been created with a string like this one:

```
SE#0.0#0.0#-1500.0#4000.0
```


Figure 2.5: An example 360-degree image

The leftmost screen on the other hand, shows *only the internal side* of the sphere; those parts of it that would show their external side result as completely transparent. A string similar to this one was used to create it:

```
SI#0.0#0.0#-1500.0#4000.0
```

This effect is impossible in real life. As it were, a spherical screen is of practical use only when its internal side is used for projecting video material - and when the observer happens to be *inside* the sphere. When this happens (using a VR visor), when the rotation of the head is detected, and when it is translated to a matching rotation of the virtual screen, the viewer perceives the view in any direction all around the point where the omnidirectional camera was located.

The effect is quickly lost if the observer *linearly* moves his/her head. The viewer could thus hope to modify the point of view, but will instead introduce warping in the visual result.

Any offset **won't** translate to the change of one's point of view, but will instead introduce warping.

3D versions of 360-degree movies can be generated. They do not include two *linearly* shifted points of view; they are instead *rotated*. At the moment of stitching together the various plane views, portions of them are chosen with the goal of reconstructing a slightly rotated point of view.

Fig. 2.6 shows the view when inside a sufficiently large spherical screen. The fish-eye-like effect is gradually lost, and a convincing impression of being immersed in the scene is obtained.

Movies

It is now possible for movies to be displayed on either a flat or a spherical screen. Movies are decoded in real time using the `ffmpeg` library⁴.

`ffmpeg` is a vast library which is able to decode practically every video format that is currently in use.

Important tip: The fact that movies are decoded live implies that much CPU and memory is required when they are displayed on stimuli screens.

Movies are imported by using the stimuli web server (see Sect. 2.6.5). The importer is responsible for classifying them as 3D or 2D, and as 360-degree or flat.

⁴See <https://ffmpeg.org>

Figure 2.6: Portion of a large spherical screen

Important tip: You are **not** forced to use flat movies on flat screen, and 360-degree movies on spherical screens, but a different association does not have practical uses.

When 3D material is displayed on Vive visors, the appropriate association of right and left-eye material with the screen portion shown to the right and left eye is used. When 3D material is displayed on 2D screens, the material for the left eye is displayed. When 2D material is displayed on a 3D visor, obviously, the same material is displayed to both eyes.

Please refer to Sects. [3.11.3](#) and [3.12.3](#), for examples of how the AV_OPEN_STILLS and, respectively, the AV_OPEN_MOVIES commands are used to communicate these parameters to the system.

Files (stills)

The still-frame visual stimuli display system is able to display any file that is found under a directory that is found on the server machine:

```
/moog_base/stills/
```

Under this directory, any number of further directories can be found, with names like:

```
hor-resxvert-res
```

For example:

```
1024x768
```

Inside these directories will be files including uncompressed pixels for images of the given dimension, encoded in 24 bit per pixel (one byte each for the red, green and blue components).

Files (movies)

The movie visual stimuli display system is able to display any file that is found under a directory that is found on the server machine:

```
/moog_base/movies/
```

This folder includes the imported movies with the names chosen when they have been imported. For each available movie, a second file exists, with the `.INFO` extension added. This file includes some data about the movie that was obtained when the import process had taken place.

Files should not be copied into this directory by hand, but only imported via the stimuli web server (see Sect. 2.6.5).

Messages

The messages to be used to handle the still-frame stimuli are described in Sect. 3.11. Those for using movies can be found in Sect. 3.12.

2.6.3 Transducer stimuli

These stimuli are files with sequential 12-bit data samples that will be fed to a digital-to-analog hardware device in order to output variable voltage to the external world.

The current Moog server contains two DAC channels. A server can connect to one or both channels.

Whenever the transmission of a file is required from a channel, the new transmission will either **substitute** the current one, or will be queued to start immediately at the end of the previous file. Transmissions on other channels will continue being played.

It is also possible to request that a *transducer emulator* be used. A window will appear on-screen with a three-part display box per requested channel, as shown in Fig. 2.7:

- an analog-meter-type indicator
- a digital value readout
- a graph of the last 10 seconds.

Files

The transducer stimuli transmission system is allowed to transmit any file that is found in a directory that is found on the server machine:

```
/moog_base/transducer_samples/
```

Files are considered as sequences of 16-bit unsigned values. The 12 least-significant bits will be transmitted from the DAC output channels as voltage, in the range specified when initializing the server.

Figure 2.7: The emulated DAC window

Messages

The messages to be used to handle the transducer stimuli are described in Sect. 3.13.

2.6.4 inquiring about the existence of a stimulus

Once the access to one of the stimulus management engines is granted, the client is given the possibility to inquire about the existence of stimuli of that category with given names.

The simple interfaces is made up of one message that the client can send to the server, with the request about the existence of one stimulus with a specific name.

The server will reply using the same mechanism for locating files that is used when making use of the stimuli. This means that, for example, in the case of visual stimuli, the check will be performed for the resolution that the engine has been initialized for.

The messages to be used to inquire about the existence of stimulus files are described in Sect. 3.14.

2.6.5 The stimuli web server

A very simple web server program has been developed to permit the generation of stimulus material. The program permits to the user who can reach the server with his browser to import audio samples and still images into the stimuli database of the server.

The server listens at port 22110.

Figure 2.8: Web server: main screen

Fig. 2.8 shows the main screen. From it you can choose whether to add audio samples or images.

Figure 2.9: Web server: audio stimulus import

When choosing the first option, you are presented with the screen that can be seen in Fig. 2.9. The **Browse** button permits you to select a file that is located on your own computer.

The software relies on the *Ffmpeg* library^a to be able to parse *any file that includes an audio track* - that is: simple audio files as well as media files (movies) that include a soundtrack. The audio content will be extracted and re-encoded as needed.

^a<http://www.ffmpeg.org>

In the **Title** field you will include the name that you will use to locate the sample when needing to play it back.

The system will refuse to overwrite an existing sample. It is up to the user to make sure that a file with the chosen name does not already exist.

When choosing the second option, you are presented with the screen that can be seen in Fig. 2.10. You will have to select one of the resolutions that have been defined. The **Browse** button permits you to select a file that is located on your own computer.

Figure 2.10: Web server: still-image stimulus import

When choosing the third option, you are presented with the screen that can be seen in Fig. 2.12. Two selections are required:

- Dimensionality:
 - **2D**: You are importing a standard 2-dimensional movie
 - **3D (horizontal)**: You are importing a 3-dimensional movie, where the frames for the two eyes are paired horizontally.
 - **3D (vertical)**: You are importing a 3-dimensional movie, where the frames for the two eyes are paired vertically.
- Movie type:
 - **Flat**: A normal movie, intended to be displayed onto a flat screen, is to be imported,
 - **360-degree**: A 360-degree movie, intended to be displayed onto a spherical screen, is to be imported,

See Fig. 2.11 for examples of frames. The **Browse** button permits you to select a file that is located on your own computer.

(a) A frame from a flat, 3D movie with horizontally paired subframes

(b) A frame from a 360-degree, 3D movie with vertically paired subframes

Figure 2.11: Sample movie frame types

Figure 2.12: Web server: movie stimulus import

When choosing the fourth option, you are presented with the screen that can be seen in Fig. 2.13. The **Browse** button permits you to select an audio file that is located on your own computer. You have to specify the frequency (samples/second) at which the audio file will be sampled.

Figure 2.13: Web server: transducer stimulus import

2.7 Visor types

While not being directly needed for running experiments on the Moog platform, a virtual reality 3D visor is employed for the two special research projects currently developed: **Efference** (see Ch. 5) and **Macaco** (see Ch. 6). It is also being used as a target for displaying virtual screens (see Sect: 2.6.2).

Driver software has been developed to make use of two types of sensors: The **HTC Vive**⁵ and the **The HTC Vive Pro**⁶. The main difference, as far as we are concerned, is in the resolution of the screen (1080x1200, or 940x1200 per eye for the **Vive** and 1440x1600, or 720x1600 per eye for the **Vive Pro**).

The visors are used for two scopes:

- Displaying a 3D-rendered binocular view on the screen.
- Using the readings from gyroscope and gravitometer that is included in these devices in order to maintain an idea of the rotational asset of the visor, and thus of the head that is wearing it.

The visor is currently **not** used to monitor the *linear* displacement of the visor. Preliminary work has been made, making use of the extremely sketchy publicly available information about the usage of so-called *lighthouses* together with these HTC-branded visors, but no usable results are currently available. It is hoped that the requirements of a specific research project will justify further work on this thorny issue.

It should be possible to switch between the two types of visors transparently. In the case of the two cited special research projects, it is sufficient to specify the type of visor to be used in the login message, as specifically mentioned in the projects' documentation.

2.7.1 UDP port raw output

The software that interprets the visor data stream and computes the current idea of the rotational asset of the visor has the possibility to stream the current visor asset to a UDP socket in real time.

As mentioned above, the visor code is not strictly part of the Moog package. This facility, and the simple data format that can be read from the socket, are described here to be of help to the user.

⁵See <https://www.vive.com/eu/product/#vive-series>

⁶See <https://www.vive.com/eu/product/#pro-series>

The UDP port to use must be specified when initializing the visor access subsystem. As of now, only the *Efference* special project makes use of the rotational asset data. See section 5.2 for the practical details.

The output is constituted of 20-byte packets, including two fields each:

- Bytes 0-3: one 32-bit integer value containing the time offset of the packet *in milliseconds* from the beginning of the *Efference* session.
- Bytes 4-19: four 32-bit floating-point values containing the quaternion that describes the rotation of the visor with reference to the last time that the visor's position was stabilized after an EFFE_CALIBRATE_VISOR message was received.

The used quaternion format is **X Y Z W**.

Chapter 3

Protocol

This chapter describes the protocol created to permit to the TPF Moog application to receive instructions from clients and to communicate status and other information to them.

Communications take place using the UDP (packet-oriented) protocol.

3.1 Ports

The system opens a listening socket at port **1860**. If no session is underway, this socket will serve the first valid login request that it receives, opening a new session. During this session, the system will *only listen to packets coming from the address and port that opened the session*. Packets coming from other addresses, as well as other login requests, will be ignored.

A second socket will be opened at local port **1966** by the system whenever a session is started. The system will write to this socket all outgoing data packets: periodic state packets, as well as specific acknowledgment messages in response to received requests.

Two special requests may be originated by clients without first logging in. Command `LIST_SESSIONS` (see sec. [3.4.9](#)) instructs the server to return a list of the tags of the sessions that took place in a given calendar day. Command `POST_PRODUCE` (see sec. [3.4.19](#)) instructs the server to run the post-production phase for a given session, and, if needed, to mail the resulting files to one or more e-mail addresses.

Both these services do not imply the creation of a session, but the usage of messages and sockets is identical for them as for sessions. Specific sockets will be closed when the request has been serviced.

3.2 Message format

All data packets will be composed and parsed as ASCII strings, composed of `comma`-separated fields.

3.2.1 Client to server

All messages sent by the client to the server will be made up of at least one field:

- The message ID (Integer)

Other `comma`-separated fields may be required by specific messages.

For example:

300,0.050000,0.000000,1500.000000,-300.000000

3.2.2 Server to client

All messages sent by the server to the client will be made up of at least two fields:

- A timestamp, in milliseconds from the start of the session (Integer)
- The message ID (Integer)

Other **comma**-separated fields may be required by specific messages.

For example:

12809,303,0,13

3.3 Message catalog

This is the catalog of existing messages. Each message will be described in its subsection.

Legenda:

- **c>s**: from client to server
- **s>c**: from server to client

ID	Tag	Direction	Description	Page
0	LOGIN	c>s	Request to access	P.44
1	LOGIN_ACK	s>c	Request to access granted	P.54
2	LOGIN_NAK	s>c	Request to access refused	P.54
3	ENGAGE	c>s	Request to engage the platform	P.42
4	ENGAGE_ACK	s>c	Request to engage granted	P.51
5	ENGAGE_NAK	s>c	Request to engage refused	P.52
6	ENGAGE_DONE	s>c	Engage completed	P.51
7	PARK	c>s	Request to park the platform	P.49
8	PARK_ACK	s>c	Request to park granted	P.57
9	PARK_NAK	s>c	Request to park refused	P.57
10	PARK_DONE	s>c	park completed	P.57
11	LOGOUT	c>s	Request to close session	P.45
12	LOGOUT_ACK	s>c	Request to close session granted	P.54
13	LOGOUT_NAK	s>c	Request to close session refused	P.55
14	IDLE_TIMEOUT	s>c	Session closed due to timeout	P.52
15	LIST_SESSIONS	c>s	Request list of sessions for a day	P.43
16	LIST_SESSIONS_SESSION	s>c	Reply with one session for a day	P.54
17	LIST_SESSIONS_NAK	s>c	List of session request unsuccessful	P.53
18	LIST_SESSIONS_DONE	s>c	List of session reply completed	P.53
19	POST_PRODUCE	c>s	Request post-production and result delivery for one session	P.49
20	POST_PRODUCE_NAK	s>c	Post-production request failed	P.58
21	POST_PRODUCE_DONE	s>c	Post-production request processed	P.57
22	ACTIVATE_HW_INPUT	c>s	Request activation of hardware input thread	P.67

ID	Tag	Direction	Description	Page
23	HW_INPUT_ACK	s>c	Hardware input thread activation granted	P.68
24	HW_INPUT_NAK	s>c	Hardware input thread activation refused	P.68
25	HW_INPUT_EVENT	s>c	Contains a hardware input thread event	P.69
26	SEED_RNDGEN	c>s	Request to the server to seed the random generator	P.49
27	GET_BRANCH	c>s	Request to the server the name of the current GIT branch in use	P.43
28	BRANCH	s>c	The name of the current GIT branch in use is returned	P.51
29	GET_TOPIC	c>s	Request to the server the name of the current topic in use	P.43
30	TOPIC	s>c	The name of the current topic in use is returned	P.60
100	STATE	s>c	Periodic state message	P.59
101	DPIN_CHANGE	s>c	Digital input pin changes state	P.51
200	IMMEDIATE_REQ	c>s	Request immediate displacement	P.43
201	IMMEDIATE_ACK	s>c	Immediate displacement accepted	P.52
202	IMMEDIATE_NAK	s>c	Immediate displacement refused	P.53
203	IMMEDIATE_AT_HEIGHT	s>c	Immediate session: required height reached	P.52
300	BEGIN_SHORT_SEQ	c>s	Begin defining short sequence	P.41
301	SHORT_SEQ_STEP	c>s	One step of a short sequence	P.50
302	COMPLETE_SHORT_SEQ	c>s	Complete short sequence definition	P.42
303	SHORT_SEQ_ACK	s>c	Short sequence definition acknowledged	P.58
304	SHORT_SEQ_NAK	s>c	Short sequence definition refused	P.59
305	SHORT_SEQ_AT_HEIGHT	s>c	Short sequence: arrived at op. height after engaging	P.58
306	SHORT_SEQ_DONE	s>c	Short sequence completed	P.59
307	SHORT_SEQ_FREEZE	c>s	Request Short sequence immediate stop	P.50
308	SHORT_SEQ_FREEZE_ACK	s>c	Short sequence immediate stop confirmed	P.58
400	BEGIN_LONG_SEQ	c>s	Begin defining long sequence	P.41
401	LONG_SEQ_STEP	c>s	One step of a long sequence	P.47
402	COMPLETE_LONG_SEQ	c>s	Complete long sequence definition	P.42
403	LONG_SEQ_ACK	s>c	Long sequence definition acknowledged	P.55
404	LONG_SEQ_NAK	s>c	Long sequence definition refused	P.56
405	LONG_SEQ_AT_HEIGHT	s>c	Long sequence: arrived at op. height after engaging	P.55
406	LONG_SEQ_AT_START	c>s	Long sequence: position at start	P.46
407	LONG_SEQ_READY	s>c	Long sequence: positioned at start	P.57
408	LONG_SEQ_EXECUTE	c>s	Execute long sequence	P.46
409	LONG_SEQ_EXECUTE_NAK	s>c	Refuse long sequence positioning or execution	P.56
410	LONG_SEQ_DONE	s>c	Long sequence completed	P.56
411	LONG_SEQ_FREEZE	c>s	Request long sequence immediate stop	P.46
412	LONG_SEQ_FREEZE_ACK	s>c	Long sequence immediate stop confirmed	P.56
413	LONG_SEQ_STEP_SINEACC	c>s	One step of a long sequence, imposing a sinewave acceleration profile	P.47
414	LONG_SEQ_STEP_DAMPEDOSC	c>s	One step of a long sequence, imposing a damped-oscillator profile	P.48
500	EFFE_ACK	s>c	Generic "Efference" acknowledge message	P.98
501	EFFE_NAK	s>c	Generic "Efference" not-acknowledge message	P.100
502	EFFE_CALIBRATE_VISOR	c>s	Requests the performance of a new visor calibration	P.92
503	EFFE_VISOR_CALIBRATED	s>c	The visor calibration process is complete	P.100
504	EFFE_SAVE_REFERENCE	c>s	During an "Efference" session, request that the current head orientation is taken as reference	P.97
505	EFFE_EXERCISEMODE_ON	c>s	Activate "Efference" exercise mode	P.92

ID	Tag	Direction	Description	Page
506	EFFE_EXERCISEMODE_OFF	c>s	Terminate “Efference” exercise mode	P.93
507	EFFE_GET_IPD	c>s	Request current value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device	P.94
508	EFFE_SET_IPD	c>s	Sets value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device	P.97
509	EFFE_IPD_VAL	s>c	Current value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device is returned	P.99
510	EFFE_TESTMODE_ON	c>s	Activate “Efference” test mode	P.98
511	EFFE_TESTMODE_OFF	c>s	Terminate “Efference” test mode	P.98
512	EFFE_GET_CURR_ANGLE	c>s	Requests, during an “Efference” session, the current yaw/pitch angle	P.94
513	EFFE_CURR_ANGLE	s>c	During an “Efference” session, the server replies with the current yaw/pitch angle	P.99
514	EFFE_BEGIN_RUN	c>s	During an “Efference” session, the request is made to start a new run	P.91
515	EFFE_POSITION	c>s	During a run of an “Efference” session, the request is made to move the platform to a new position	P.95
516	EFFE_RUN_TEST	c>s	During a run of an “Efference” session, the request is made to perform a test	P.96
517	EFFE_EVALUATE	c>s	During a run of an “Efference” session, the request is made to allow the subject to perform an evaluation	P.92
518	EFFE_COMPLETE_RUN	c>s	During an “Efference” session, the request is made to complete the run that is currently underway	P.92
519	EFFE_PARK	c>s	Require parking (and thus session end) from “Efference”	P.95
520	EFFE_INTERPOL_DATA	c>s	Pass the interpolation parameters that will be used for subsequent “Efference” tests	P.94
600	AV_AUDIO_ACK	s>c	Acknowledges an audio stimuli command	P.69
601	AV_AUDIO_NAK	s>c	Rejects an audio stimuli command	P.69
602	AV_OPEN_AUDIO	c>s	Requests the opening of the audio output subsystem	P.69
603	AV_AUDIO_PLAY	c>s	Requests the playback of an audio sample on a channel	P.70
604	AV_AUDIO_STOP	c>s	Requests the interruption of playback of a channel	P.70
605	AV_AUDIO_STOP_ALL	c>s	Requests the interruption of playback of all channels	P.70
606	AV_AUDIO_SAMPLE_ENDED	s>c	Communicates that the playback of a sample has concluded	P.71
620	AV_STILLS_ACK	s>c	Acknowledges a still-frame stimuli command	P.71
621	AV_STILLS_NAK	s>c	Rejects a still-frame stimuli command	P.71
622	AV_OPEN_STILLS	c>s	Requests the opening of the video still-frame output subsystem	P.71
623	AV_STILLS_STILL	c>s	Requests the display of one specific still-frame image on one screen	P.73
624	AV_STILLS_FILL_RGB	c>s	Requests one screen of the still-frame display to be filled up in one 24-bit color	P.73
625	AV_STILLS_ACTIVATE	c>s	Requests one screen of the still-frame display to be activated	P.74
626	AV_STILLS_DEACTIVATE	c>s	Requests one screen of the still-frame display to be deactivated	P.74

ID	Tag	Direction	Description	Page
627	AV_STILLS_GET_IPD	c>s	Request current value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device	P.74
628	AV_STILLS_SET_IPD	c>s	Sets value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device	P.74
629	AV_STILLS_IPD_VAL	s>c	Current value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device is returned	P.75
630	AV_STILLS_ROTATE_SCREEN	c>s	Requests the arbitrary rotation of a (spherical) still-image screen	P.75
640	AV_TRANSD_ACK	s>c	Acknowledges a transducer stimuli command	P.78
641	AV_TRANSD_NAK	s>c	Rejects a transducer stimuli command	P.78
642	AV_OPEN_TRANSD	c>s	Requests the opening of the transducer output subsystem	P.78
643	AV_TRANSD_PLAY	c>s	Requests the transmission of a transducer file on a channel	P.79
644	AV_TRANSD_STOP	c>s	Requests the interruption of transmission of a channel	P.80
645	AV_TRANSD_CHANNEL_IDLE	s>c	Communicates that one of the transducer channels has become idle	P.80
660	AV_MOVIES_ACK	s>c	Acknowledges a movie stimuli command	P.75
661	AV_MOVIES_NAK	s>c	Rejects a movie stimuli command	P.75
662	AV_OPEN_MOVIES	c>s	Requests the opening of the video movie output subsystem	P.76
663	AV_MOVIES_MOVIE	c>s	Requests the display of one specific movie on one screen	P.76
664	AV_MOVIES_ROTATE_SCREEN	c>s	Requests the arbitrary rotation of a (spherical) movie screen	P.76
665	AV_MOVIES_PAUSE	c>s	Requests the playback of a movie to be paused or resumed	P.77
666	AV_MOVIES_FILL_RGB	c>s	Requests one screen of the movie display to be filled up in one 24-bit color	P.77
667	AV_MOVIES_GET_IPD	c>s	Request current value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device	P.77
668	AV_MOVIES_SET_IPD	c>s	Sets value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device	P.77
669	AV_MOVIES_IPD_VAL	s>c	Current value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device is returned	P.78
680	AV_INQUIRE	c>s	The client inquires about the existence of a stimulus file	P.80
681	AV_INQUIRE_REPLY	s>c	The server replies to the client about the existence of a stimulus file	P.81
700	MACACO_REGENERATE_TRIAS	c>s	From "Macaco" mode, the client requests the set of triangles to be regenerated	P.109
701	MACACO_RUN_TASK	c>s	Run a "Macaco" task	P.110
702	MACACO_ABORT_TASK	c>s	Abort a running "Macaco" task	P.111
703	MACACO_TASK_ACK	s>c	Accept the request of a "Macaco" standard task	P.112
704	MACACO_TASK_NAK	s>c	Reject the request of a "Macaco" task	P.112
705	MACACO_TASK_COMPLETED	s>c	Report on the completion of a "Macaco" task	P.113
706	MACACO_GET_IPD	c>s	Request current value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device	P.111
707	MACACO_SET_IPD	c>s	Sets value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device	P.112
708	MACACO_IPD_VAL	s>c	Current value of interpupillary distance for the head-mounted device is returned	P.114

ID	Tag	Direction	Description	Page
709	MACACO_PARK	c>s	Require parking (and thus session end) from “Macaco”	P.112
710	MACACO_ENGAGED	s>c	“Macaco” session: Server confirms engagement and positioning	P.112
711	MACACO_BEGIN_CAPTURE	c>s	Request video capture during a “Macaco” session	P.111
712	MACACO_END_CAPTURE	c>s	Request completion of a video capture during a “Macaco” session	P.111
713	MACACO_TESTMODE_ON	c>s	Activate “Macaco” test mode	P.109
714	MACACO_TESTMODE_OFF	c>s	Terminate “Macaco” test mode	P.109
715	MACACO_RUN_TASK_RING	c>s	Run a “Macaco” <i>ring</i> task	P.110

3.4 Client-to-server messages

3.4.1 BEGIN_LONG_SEQ (400)

During a long-sequence session, the client announces that it begins to define one sequence.

Five parameters must follow the command:

- The name of the sequence. If a sequence already exists with this name, the old sequence will be erased, and substituted with the new one.
- The maximum *actuator motion* speed permitted at any moment during the sequence, in metres/second.
- Three parameters, indicating the center of rotation that will be used for any rotation motion included in the sequence. In metres, in Moog order (heave, surge, lateral).

Possible outcomes:

- LONG_SEQ_NAK: The server is not in idle state, too few parameters have been passed, or another sequence is already being defined.

Example:

```
400,t_roll,0.14,0.0,0.0,0.0
```

3.4.2 BEGIN_SHORT_SEQ (300)

During a short-sequence session, the client announces that it wants to define a sequence. These parameters are required:

- The maximum *actuator motion* speed permitted at any moment during the sequence, in metres/second.
- Three parameters, indicating the center of rotation that will be used for any rotation motion included in the sequence. In metres, in Moog order (heave, surge, lateral).

Possible outcomes:

- SHORT_SEQ_NAK: The server is not in engaged state, or another sequence is already being defined.

Example:

```
300,0.050000,-1.5,0.3,0.0
```

3.4.3 COMPLETE_LONG_SEQ (402)

The client, while defining a sequence in the preliminary phase of a long-sequence session, communicates that the sequence definition has been completed.

Possible outcomes:

- LONG_SEQ_ACK: The sequence has been accepted.
- LONG_SEQ_NAK: The client has not begun the definition of a sequence, the sequence is empty, or it has not passed the speed test.

Example:

402

3.4.4 COMPLETE_SHORT_SEQ (302)

The client, while defining a sequence during a short-sequence session, communicates that the sequence definition has been completed.

Possible outcomes:

- SHORT_SEQ_ACK: The sequence has been accepted, and then platform is moving towards the operative height.
- SHORT_SEQ_AT_HEIGHT (later): The platform has reached the operative height, and the sequence is being performed.
- SHORT_SEQ_DONE: (later): The sequence performance has been concluded.
- SHORT_SEQ_NAK: The client had not begun the definition of a sequence, the sequence is empty, or it has not passed the speed test.

Example:

302

3.4.5 ENGAGE (3)

The client, while running a session, requests the engagement of the platform.

Possible outcomes:

- ENGAGE_ACK: The request has been accepted, and the engagement procedure is underway.
- ENGAGE_DONE (later): The engagement procedure has successfully concluded.
- ENGAGE_NAK: The server is not in idle state, and thus cannot engage.

Example:

3

3.4.6 GET_BRANCH (27)

When this message is received, the server replies with message BRANCH (see Sect. 3.5.1) containing the name of the *branch* that the MOO-Standardone GIT repository from which the server is executed is at.

Example:

```
27
```

3.4.7 GET_TOPIC (29)

When this message is received, the server replies with message TOPIC (see Sect. 3.5.35) containing the name of the *topic* that the currently executing server is associated to. See App. A for more information about topics.

Example:

```
29
```

3.4.8 IMMEDIATE_REQ (200)

While in an Immediate session, the client submits a new set of DoF values where the platform has to move. The move is immediately performed, if possible.

Seven parameters are required:

- Step ID: an integer identifying this step. The value must be an integer, but no other check is made on it. This identifier will be mentioned in the acknowledgment message, making it possible for the client to verify which steps have been correctly performed.
- The degree-of-freedom values to be attained, in Moog order (ROLL, PITCH, heave, surge, YAW, lateral).

Possible outcomes:

- IMMEDIATE_ACK: The request has been accepted, and the motion is being attempted.
- IMMEDIATE_NAK: Either the platform is not engaged, or the motion violates the linear/angular speed limit.

Example:

```
200,0,-0.000000,0.000000,-0.100000,0.000000,0.000000,-0.000000
```

3.4.9 LIST_SESSIONS (15)

While a session is **not underway**, the client requests the list of sessions that have been run during a specific day.

One parameter is required:

- The date, in YYMMDD format.

Possible outcomes:

- `MSG_LIST_SESSIONS_SESSION`: The request has been accepted, and the message contains details for one session.
- `MSG_LIST_SESSIONS_DONE` (eventually): Sent by the server at end of the list.
- `MSG_LIST_SESSIONS_NAK`: The date could not be found.

Example:

15,190826

3.4.10 LOGIN (0)

Sent by the prospective client to gain access to the system, in order to run a session of a given type. The client will have to pass a different set of parameter according to the session type.

The first two parameters are common for each session:

- The session type (see Table 3.2).
- The UDP port of the client's incoming socket.

Code	Description
1	Immediate
2	Short sequence
3	Long sequence
4	Joystick
5	Efference (see Ch. 5)
6	Macaco (see Ch. 6)

Table 3.2: The session types

Immediate session

Three additional parameters are required when starting an immediate session:

- The maximum accepted difference between the current and the requested values of the three linear degrees of freedom, expressed in metres.
- The maximum accepted difference between the current and the requested values of the three angular degrees of freedom, expressed in radians.
- The height at which the platform has to be positioned after engaging, in metres (*negative upwards!*)

Short sequence session

Two additional parameters are required when starting a short-sequence session:

- The specification of whether the platform will be steered by passing it the actuator lengths (letter **L**) or the degree-of-freedom values (letter **D**).
- The height at which the platform has to be positioned after engaging, in metres (*negative upwards!*)

Long sequence session

Two additional parameters are required when starting a long-sequence session:

- The specification of whether the platform will be steered by passing it the actuator lengths (letter **L**) or the degree-of-freedom values (letter **D**).
- The height at which the platform has to be positioned after engaging, in metres (*negative upwards!*)

Joystick session

Four additional parameters are required when starting an immediate session:

- The maximum actuator velocity, in metres/second, that will be enforced when receiving input data from the joystick: if the joystick motion would result in a faster required displacement on any actuator, the movement will be appropriately clamped.
- The center of rotation, in moog coordinates (Heave, Surge, Lateral - in metres) around which the platform will appear to be rotating

For all session types: button labels

Up to eight labels to assign to the buttons connected to the digital input-output device. Empty strings (two commas one after the other) indicate that the button should not be used.

Possible outcomes:

- LOGIN_ACK: the session was successfully opened.
- LOGIN_NAK: Login was unsuccessful. The Moog platform may have been off-line, a session by another client may already be underway, the session type was not valid, or parameters were wrong.

Example:

```
0,2,47476,D,-0.2,,Right,,Left
```

This example logs in for a short-sequence session, requests that the platform is commanded by passing it degree-of-freedom values, indicates an operative height of -0.2 metres, and requests that buttons connected to the second and fourth connector block be associated to button labels “Right” and “Left.” All other buttons will not be considered for the run.

3.4.11 LOGOUT (11)

Sent to request a clean termination of the current session. The request will be honored only if the system is currently in IDLE mode.

The system will reply either with a LOGOUT_ACK, indicating that the session was successfully closed, or with a LOGOUT_NAK message, indicating that something went wrong.

The command may be followed by parameters. if so, the *first parameter* will include the time rate of the resulting post-production file in milliseconds, and any further parameter will specify an e-mail address (in the university domain) to which the results of the post-production phase will be sent.

Example:

```
11,500,daniel.fitze@psy.unibe.ch
```

3.4.12 LONG_SEQ_FREEZE (411)

The client requests that the long sequence being run is brought to an immediate halt, effectively stopping the motion of the platform at whatever position it happens to be.

When an emergency freeze is required, it can only be cleanly exited by pressing the on-screen button labeled **ABORT SESSION**. When the button is pressed, the session that is underway is cleanly closed.

Possible outcomes:

- LONG_SEQ_FREEZE_ACK: The freezing action is confirmed.

Example:

```
411
```

3.4.13 LONG_SEQ_AT_START (406)

The client, during a long-sequence session, after having engaged the platform, requests that the platform is moved to the position corresponding to the first step of one sequence.

The motion from the current platform position to the required start position is first tested for validity.

One parameter is required:

- The name of the sequence.

Possible outcomes:

- LONG_SEQ_READY: The platform has moved to the position with which the requested sequence begins.
- LONG_SEQ_EXECUTE_NAK: a sequence is already underway, the requested session does not exist, no session was specified, or motion to the first step of the could not be validated.

Example:

```
406,t_roll
```

3.4.14 LONG_SEQ_EXECUTE (409)

The client, during a long-sequence session, requests that the sequence that was previously positioned to start is performed.

Possible outcomes:

- LONG_SEQ_DONE (eventually): The platform has completed the sequence.
- LONG_SEQ_EXECUTE_NAK: No sequence has been positioned at start, or the sequence is already executing.

Example:

```
409
```

3.4.15 LONG_SEQ_STEP (401)

The client, during a long-sequence session, is defining one long sequence, and sends the next step of the session. Eight parameters are required:

- The degree-of-freedom values to be attained, in Moog order (ROLL, PITCH, heave, surge, YAW, lateral).
- The time, in seconds, that the motion must last.
- The law followed for the motion. Current valid values are:
 - **L**: Linear.
 - **S**: Sinusoid.
 - **C**: Casteljau, with steps of 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, 1.0, 1.0.

Possible outcomes:

- LONG_SEQ_NAK: No sequence is being defined, or the syntax is bad.

Example:

```
401,-0.0,-0.0,-0.2,0.0,0.0,0.0,10.0,S
```

3.4.16 LONG_SEQ_STEP_SINEACC (413)

The client, during a long-sequence session, is defining one long sequence, and sends the next step of the session. The acceleration of the step is requested to have a sinewave profile.

Label	Provided parameter #1	Provided parameter #2	Provided parameter #3	Calculated parameter #1	Calculated parameter #2
BOTH_LIN_ANG_ACC	Max. linear acceleration	Linear displacement	Max. angular acceleration	Time	Angular displacement
BOTH_LIN_ANG_DISP	Max. linear acceleration	Linear displacement	Angular displacement	Time	Max. angular acceleration
BOTH_ANG_LIN_ACC	Max. angular acceleration	Angular displacement	Max. linear acceleration	Time	Linear displacement
BOTH_ANG_LIN_DISP	Max. angular acceleration	Angular displacement	Linear displacement	Time	Max. linear acceleration
LIN_ACC_ANG_ACC_TIME	Max. linear acceleration	Max. angular acceleration	Time	Linear displacement	Angular displacement
LIN_ACC_ANG_DISP_TIME	Max. linear acceleration	Angular displacement	Time	Linear displacement	Max. angular acceleration
LIN_DISP_ANG_ACC_TIME	Linear displacement	Max. angular acceleration	Time	Max. linear acceleration	Angular displacement
LIN_DISP_ANG_DISP_TIME	Linear displacement	Angular displacement	Time	Max. linear acceleration	Max. angular acceleration

Table 3.3: The types of sinewave acceleration interpolations, defined by the parameters that the user has to provide.

This type of interpolation (see Sect. 1.3.4) requires the specification of three parameters, different for each interpolation subtype. Table 3.3 contains the names of the subtypes, and the three parameters that must be submitted plus the two that will be returned for each subtype.

Ten parameters are required:

- The name of the subtype (as found in the first column of Table 3.3).
- One value for each degree-of-freedom, that will build two vectors indicating the direction of linear motion (third, fourth and sixth values) and that of angular motion (first, second and fifth values). **These vectors will be normalized.** The actual length of the displacement will be either provided or calculated (linear / angular displacement).
- The values of the three parameters to be provided, as indicated in columns 2-4 of Table 3.3.

Example:

```
413,LIN_DISP_ANG_DISP_TIME,0.005236,-0.005236,0.464700,0.000100,0.006981,0.000300,
100.000000,0.139626,15.000000
```

The two calculated parameters will be returned as parameters of message LONG_SEQ_ACK (see Sect. 3.5.17).

3.4.17 LONG_SEQ_STEP_DAMPEDOSC (414)

The client, during a long-sequence session, is defining one long sequence, and sends the next step of the session. The step is requested to have a damped-oscillation interpolation profile.

This type of interpolation (see Sect. 1.3.5) requires the specification of eleven parameters:

- 1-6: the six degree-of-freedom target values, as specified for the simple LONG_SEQ_STEP command.
- 7: The value of the mass of the virtual object that is supposed to oscillate (the bigger the mass, the slower and more extreme the oscillation will be).
- 8: The value of the so-called *spring constant* of the object. The higher the value, the harder it will be for the spring to extend.
- 9: The damping factor. The higher the value, the quicker the system will stop the oscillation.
- 10: The maximum duration of the step.
- 11: The lower threshold of the energy level. When the system reaches this level, the motion will stop.

Important tip: You cannot specify a precise time for this motion. You specify a maximum limit. If the system reaches a state of quiet (energy lower than the passed threshold), the motion will last for that duration. Otherwise, it will be extended to the whole maximum-duration length, at which time the motion will suddenly stop.

Example:

```
414,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.230000,0.000000,0.069813,0.000000,1.100000,5.500000,0.700000,
50.000000,0.000500
```

A flag indicating if the dampening was successful, along with the actual duration of the motion, will be returned as parameters of message LONG_SEQ_ACK (see Sect. 3.5.17).

3.4.18 PARK (7)

The client, while running a session, requests that the platform be disengaged and parked.

Possible outcomes:

- PARK_ACK: The request has been accepted, and the parking procedure is underway.
- PARK_DONE (later): The parking procedure has successfully concluded.
- PARK_NAK: The server is not in engaged state, and thus cannot park.

Example:

```
7
```

3.4.19 POST_PRODUCE (19)

While a session is **not underway**, the client requests that the post-production process is run, if necessary, for a given session, and that the results are sent to one or more e-mail addresses.

Two parameters are required:

- The date and time of the session, in `YYMMDD.hhmmss` format.
- The required data record interval in milliseconds.

Furthermore, any number of additional parameters may follow. Each parameter must contain one valid e-mail address from the `unibe.ch` domain.

Possible outcomes:

- POST_PRODUCE_DONE: The process was completed.
- POST_PRODUCE_NAK: a bad date/time tag was passed, no session corresponds to that tag, or some errors were encountered in the post-processing or mailing phases.

Example:

```
19,190826.091243,200,matthias.ertl@psy.unibe.ch
```

3.4.20 SEED_RNDGEN (26)

Whenever a session is underway, the client can ask the server to seed its pseudo-random number generator, so that runs based on random numbers may receive equal streams of random data.

Both the C (see the manual page for the POSIX function `srand48`) and the Ruby generators will be seeded.

Important tip: You will be assured that the stream of numbers will be equal, but if you request actions in different order, or skip/add steps that use random numbers, you will have different streams of numbers applied to the various users from the moment the order is modified.

For example, if your subjects interrupt a sequence of events that consume random numbers along time at different moments, the consumption of random numbers will lose sync.

This request can be submitted as often as needed.

One parameter may be passed:

- The seed to use. **If no parameter is passed, the value of the operating system's idea of time in seconds is used, with the result that a different stream of pseudo-random numbers are generated.**

Example:

```
26,76543
```

The client won't receive an acknowledgment, but a line will mark the successful seeding in the log file.

3.4.21 SHORT_SEQ_FREEZE (307)

The client requests that the short sequence being run is brought to an immediate halt, effectively stopping the motion of the platform at whatever position it happens to be.

When an emergency freeze is required, it can only be cleanly exited by pressing the on-screen button labeled **ABORT SESSION**. When the button is pressed, the session that is underway is cleanly closed.

Possible outcomes:

- SHORT_SEQ_FREEZE_ACK: The freezing action is confirmed.

Example:

```
307
```

3.4.22 SHORT_SEQ_STEP (301)

The client, during a short-sequence session, is defining one short sequence, and sends the next step of the session.

Eight parameters are required:

- The degree-of-freedom values to be attained, in Moog order (ROLL, PITCH, heave, surge, YAW, lateral).
- The time, in seconds, that the motion must last.
- The law followed for the motion. Current valid values are:
 - **L**: Linear.
 - **S**: Sinusoid.
 - **C**: Casteljau, with steps of 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, 1.0, 1.0.

Possible outcomes:

- SHORT_SEQ_NAK: No sequence is being defined, a short sequence is currently being run, or the syntax is bad.

Example:

```
301,-0.0,-0.0,-0.15,0.0,0.0,0.0,5.0,S
```

3.5 Server-to-client messages

3.5.1 BRANCH (28)

The server replies with this message when the client sends a GET_BRANCH message, requiring the name of the **GIT** branch that the server being executed is at.

The message will contain one parameter:

- The name of the **GIT** branch

Example:

```
12345,28,macaco
```

3.5.2 DPIN_CHANGE (101)

The server communicates that one of the buttons connected to the system has changed state.

The message will contain three parameters:

- The name of the button (the same string that was used in the LOGIN message).
- A **1** if the button has been pressed, a **0** if the button has been released.
- The timestamp of the actual event (typically, a few milliseconds before the timestamp of the received message).

Example:

```
12345,101,"red",1,12340
```

3.5.3 ENGAGE_ACK (4)

The system communicates that a request for engaging has been received and is being processed.

Example:

```
12345,4
```

3.5.4 ENGAGE_DONE (6)

The system communicates that the engaging procedure has completed with success.

Example:

```
12345,6
```

3.5.5 ENGAGE_NAK (5)

The system communicates that the engaging procedure could not be performed.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A short description of the reason of the failure.

Example:

```
12345,5,"NOT IDLE"
```

3.5.6 IDLE_TIMEOUT (14)

The server communicates that a session remained idle for too long. After this message is sent, the server closes the session.

Example:

```
12345,14
```

3.5.7 IMMEDIATE_ACK (201)

When running in immediate mode, every step that the client requests by sending an IMMEDIATE_REQ message is acknowledged, if successful, with this message.

The message will contain one parameter:

- The ID of the immediate step being acknowledged, as passed by the client in the IMMEDIATE_REQ message.

Example:

```
12345,201,33
```

3.5.8 IMMEDIATE_AT_HEIGHT (203)

When starting an immediate session, the server communicates to the client that it has successfully reached the operative height.

This message is sent by the client just before confirming that the *engage* process was completed successfully, with a ENGAGE_DONE message.

Example:

```
12345,203
```

3.5.9 IMMEDIATE_NAK (202)

When running in immediate mode, for every step that the client requests by sending an IMMEDIATE_REQ message and which could not be performed for some reason, the server will generate an IMMEDIATE_NAK message.

The message will contain three parameters.

- If the move failed because the length limit for an actuator had been hit:
 - The letter **A**.
 - The progressive number of the actuator.
 - The faulty value.
- If the move failed because a speed limit has been hit:
 - The letter **L**.
 - The progressive number of the degree of freedom (in MOOG order).
 - The difference value to the hit limit..

Example:

```
12345,202,A,2,0.5
```

3.5.10 LIST_SESSIONS_DONE (18)

When a list of sessions for some date has been requested (with message LIST_SESSIONS), the server sends this message after records for each existing session, to indicate that the task has been completed. After this message is sent, the socket link is broken.

Example:

```
0,18
```

(the time flag for server messages generated during this conversation is set to 0.)

3.5.11 LIST_SESSIONS_NAK (17)

After a list of sessions for some date has been requested, the server replies with this message if the request could not be completed.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A brief explanation of the reason for the refusal.

Example:

```
0,17,"date not found"
```

(the time flag for server messages generated during this conversation is set to 0.)

3.5.12 LIST_SESSIONS_SESSION (16)

After a list of sessions for some date has been requested, the server sends a message with this ID for each existing session that took place in the given date.

The message will contain three parameters:

- The time stamp of the session (in `hhmmss` format).
- The IP address from which the session was initiated.
- The session type (see Table 3.2).

Example:

```
0,16,091730,"192.168.1.200","Long sequences"
```

(the time flag for server messages generated during this conversation is set to 0.)

3.5.13 LOGIN_ACK (1)

The server sends this message to confirm that a login request has been accepted and a session is open.

The message will contain one parameter:

- The time.date stamp of the session (in `YYMMDD.hhmmss` format).

Example:

```
12345,1,190826.113058
```

3.5.14 LOGIN_NAK (2)

The server sends this message to communicate that a login request could not be accepted.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A brief explanation of the reason for the refusal.

Example:

```
12345,2,"session underway"
```

3.5.15 LOGOUT_ACK (12)

The server sends this message to confirm that a logout request has been accepted. The network link will be cut right after the message is sent.

Example:

```
12345,12
```

3.5.16 LOGOUT_NAK (13)

The server sends this message to communicate that a logout request could not be honoured.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A brief explanation of the reason for the refusal.

Example:

```
12345,13,"NOT IDLE"
```

3.5.17 LONG_SEQ_ACK (403)

From within a long-sequence session, the server confirms that a sequence has been successfully defined.

The message will contain at least these three parameters:

- The name of the sequence, as set by the client with the `BEGIN_LONG_SEQ` command.
- The number of steps that are included in the sequence.
- The maximum speed detected when validating the sequence.

Furthermore, three pipe-separated parameters will be present for each step that was submitted with message `LONG_SEQ_STEP_SINEACC`:

- A letter **A** followed by the progressive number of the step in the sequence, beginning with zero.
- The values for the two calculated parameters listed for the step subtype (see Table 3.3 on P.47).

three pipe-separated parameters will also be present for each step that was submitted with message `LONG_SEQ_STEP_DAMPEDOSC`:

- A letter **D** followed by the progressive number of the step in the sequence, beginning with zero.
- The string **Damped** if the motion was damped before the provided maximum duration, or the string **Not damped** otherwise.
- The actual duration of the step's motion.

Example:

```
12345,403,t_roll,4,0.038657,A1|2.792521|0.003901,D2|Damped|13.450000
```

3.5.18 LONG_SEQ_AT_HEIGHT (405)

From within a long-sequence session, the server communicates that it has reached the operative height, and it is thus possible for the client to request the run of defined sequences.

Example:

```
12345,405
```

3.5.19 LONG_SEQ_DONE (410)

From within a long-sequence session, the server communicates that it has completed the execution of the current sequence.

The message will contain one parameter:

- The name of the sequence whose execution has been completed.

Example:

```
12345,410,t_roll
```

3.5.20 LONG_SEQ_EXECUTE_NAK (409)

From within a long-sequence session, the server communicates that it could not proceed, for some reason, to execute a sequence.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A brief explanation of the reason for the refusal.

Example:

```
12345,409,"Bad start syntax"
```

3.5.21 LONG_SEQ_FREEZE_ACK (412)

The server, during a long-sequence session, sends this message to communicate that it has complied with the request to freeze the platform position. The request may have come from the client, from the UI screen or due to the activation of the emergency stop button.

Example:

```
12345,412
```

When an emergency freeze is required, it can only be cleanly exited by pressing the on-screen button labeled **ABORT SESSION**. When the button is pressed, the session that is underway is cleanly closed.

3.5.22 LONG_SEQ_NAK (404)

The server, during a long-sequence session, sends this message to communicate that it could not accept the definition of a sequence.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A brief explanation of the reason for the refusal.

Example:

```
12345,404,"Bad begin"
```

3.5.23 LONG_SEQ_READY (407)

The server, during a long-sequence session, communicates that a session has the positioning at start of one sequence has been completed.

The message will contain one parameter:

- The name of the sequence

Example:

```
12345,407,t_roll
```

3.5.24 PARK_ACK (8)

The system communicates that a request for parking has been received and is being processed.

Example:

```
12345,8
```

3.5.25 PARK_DONE (10)

The system communicates that the parking procedure has completed with success.

Example:

```
12345,10
```

3.5.26 PARK_NAK (9)

The system communicates that the parking procedure could not be performed.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A short description of the reason of the failure.

Example:

```
12345,9,"NOT ENGAGED"
```

3.5.27 POST_PRODUCE_DONE (21)

When the client has requested the execution of the post-production step for a session (with message POST_PRODUCE), the server sends this message to indicate that the task has been completed. After this message is sent, the socket link is broken.

Example:

```
0,21
```

(the time flag for server messages generated during this conversation is set to 0.)

3.5.28 POST_PRODUCE_NAK (20)

When the client has requested the execution of the post-production step for a session, the server replies with this message if the request could not be completed.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A brief explanation of the reason for the refusal.

Example:

```
0,20,"bad tag"
```

(the time flag for server messages generated during this conversation is set to 0.)

3.5.29 SHORT_SEQ_FREEZE_ACK (308)

The server, during a short-sequence session, sends this message to communicate that it has complied with the request to freeze the platform position. The request may have come from the client, from the UI screen or due to the activation of the emergency stop button.

Example:

```
12345,308
```

When an emergency freeze is required, it can only be cleanly exited by pressing the on-screen button labeled **ABORT SESSION**. When the button is pressed, the session that is underway is cleanly closed.

3.5.30 SHORT_SEQ_ACK (303)

From within a short-sequence session, the server confirms that a sequence has been successfully defined, and its execution is about to begin.

The message will contain three parameters:

- A progressive number assigned to this session by the server.
- The number of steps that are included in the sequence.
- The maximum speed detected when validating the sequence.

Example:

```
12345,303,0,7
```

3.5.31 SHORT_SEQ_AT_HEIGHT (305)

From within a short-sequence session, the server communicates that it has reached the operative height, and it is thus possible for the client to request the run of sequences.

Example:

```
12345,305
```

3.5.32 SHORT_SEQ_DONE (306)

From within a long-sequence session, the server communicates that it has completed the execution of the current sequence.

The message will contain two parameters:

- The progressive numerical ID assigned to this sequence by the server.
- The number of steps that were included in the sequence.

Example:

```
12345,306,0,7
```

3.5.33 SHORT_SEQ_NAK (304)

The server, during a short-sequence session, sends this message to communicate that it could not accept the definition of a sequence.

The message will contain either one parameter:

- A brief explanation of the reason for the refusal.

or 16 parameters:

- The time (in msec from beginning of sequence) where the limit was hit.
- The element in the sequence where the limit was hit.
- The time (in msec from beginning of the faulty element) where the limit was hit.
- Which actuator was responsible for hitting the limit.
- A string describing the error type.
- The six DoF values at the moment the limit was hit.
- The six actuator lengths (in mm) at the moment the limit was hit.

Example:

```
12345,304,627,1,127,1,"Too  
→ fast",-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.200000,0.005754,0.000000,0.000000,853.666504,849.717041,855.881836,849.881836,849.881836,849.881836,849.881836,849.881836,849.881836,849.881836
```

3.5.34 STATE (100)

The server communicates the current state. This message is sent every time the platform provides a new status record.

These parameters are sent:

- The current master state (see Table 3.4)
- The current server state (see Table 3.5)

Code	Description
0	Idle
1	Engaging
2	Engaged
3	Parking
4	Fault

Table 3.4: The master states

Code	Description
0	Off
1	Idle
2	Engaging
3	Engaged
4	Wait for parking
5	Parking
6	Reset
7	Fault

Table 3.5: The server states

- The current Moog platform state (see Table 3.6)
- The six values corresponding to the reported state of the platform. They are either the current lengths of the six actuators, or the degree-of-freedom values, in this order:
 - Roll (angle, in radians)
 - Pitch (angle, in radians)
 - Heave (linear, in metres)
 - Surge (linear, in metres)
 - Yaw (angle, in radians)
 - Lateral (linear, in metres)

Example:

```
76,100,1,2,1,0.000001,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.000001,0.000000
```

3.5.35 TOPIC (30)

The server replies with this message when the client sends a GET_TOPIC message, requiring the name of the topic that the currently executing server is associated to. See App. A for more information about topics.

The message will contain one parameter:

- The name of the topic

Example:

```
12345,30,effe2
```

Code	Description
0	Power up
1	Idle
2	Standby
3	Engaged
7	Parking
8	Fault 1
9	Fault 2
10	Fault 3
11	Disabled
12	Inhibited

Table 3.6: The Moog platform states

3.6 Short sequence example

Here is a commented example for a run executing a short sequence. A *red* tab indicates a message from client to server. A *green* tab indicates a message from server to client.

| 0,2,47476,D,-0.2,red,yellow

Login request, for *short sequence mode*. Listening socket is open on port **47476**. The platform will be commanded by sending it degree-of-freedom values, and the operative height will be of -0.2 metres. Buttons connected to inputs #1 and #2 will be monitored, and their activity, both in reply messages and in log files, will be associated to the given labels.

| 1016,1,190823.084514

Acknowledgment of successful session opening, at 1016 milliseconds from beginning of session. The third field indicates the server's time stamp for the opened session (in the case above, August 23rd 08:45:14).

| 1020,100,0,1,0,0.000001,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.000001,0.000000

This is the first STATE (**100**) message that the server sends to the client. It is sent 1020 milliseconds after session opening, and indicates a master state of 0 (Idle), a server state of 1 (Idle) and a Moog status of 0 (Power up),

| 3

The client sends an ENGAGE request.

| 2000,4

At 2 seconds from session start, the server confirms that the engaging request was successfully sent (ENGAGE_ACK). At this point, the platform will start moving up to the requested operative height.

| 15225,305

At 15.2 seconds, the server sends a SHORT_SEQ_AT_HEIGHT message, indicating that the operative height has been reached.

| 15225,6

At the same time, the server confirms that the engage process was completed by sending an `ENGAGE_DONE` message. The first state message after that is as follows:

```
15235,100,2,3,3,0.000109,0.000171,-0.201230,0.000010,-0.000027,-0.000041
```

showing a master state of 2 (Engaged), a server state of 3 (Engaged) and a Moog state of 3 (Engaged). At this point, requests for short sequences and for parking may be accepted.

```
300,0.100000,0.000000,0.000000,0.000000
```

The client requires to define a short motion sequence (`BEGIN_SHORT_SEQ`).

```
301,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.150000,0.000000,0.000000,0.000000,5.000000,S  
...
```

The client then sends one or more `SHORT_SEQ_STEP` messages, one for each of the steps of the motion that the short sequence has to be composed.

```
302
```

The client sends a `COMPLETE_SHORT_SEQ` message, indicating that the sequence is complete.

```
15319,303,0,7
```

The server **validates the sequence**, communicates with a `SHORT_SEQ_ACK` message, that the sequence has been approved, and **begins to execute the sequence**.

The server communicates that this sequence has been assigned a progressive value of 0, and it is composed of 7 steps.

```
31122,101,"red",1,31113  
31404,101,"yellow",1,31394  
31425,101,"red",0,31423  
31508,101,"red",1,31503  
31571,101,"yellow",0,31564  
31633,101,"red",0,31633
```

While the sequence is being executed, buttons generate some events (message `DPIN_CHANGE`).

```
52327,306,0,7
```

At conclusion of execution, a `SHORT_SEQ_DONE` is sent, confirming the progressive number and number of steps of the sequence.

```
7
```

At this point, the client requests that the Moog platform initiate a parking sequence (`PARK`).

```
52337,8
```

The server confirms that the park request has been received (`PARK_ACK`).

```
59438,10
```

The server communicates that the parking process has been completed (PARK_DONE).

```
11,100,carlo.prelz@humdek.unibe.ch
```

The client requests to close the session (message LOGOUT). It passes the time rate of the resulting post-production file in milliseconds and e-mail address to which post-production data will be sent.

```
61177,12
```

The server confirms the logout request with a LOGOUT_ACK message, and closes the outgoing socket.

3.7 Long sequence example

In this second commented example, the creation and subsequent execution of two long sequences is demonstrated. Again, a *red* tab indicates a message from client to server, and a *green* tab indicates a message from server to client.

```
0,3,33428,L,-0.3
```

In the login request, type **3** indicates a long-sequence run.

```
0,1,190823.085243
```

Opening is acknowledged. Session begin time is this time August, 23rd, at 08:52:43.

```
10,100,0,1,0,0.000001,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.000001,0.000000
```

As in the example above, once the session is open, the server starts sending its STATE (**100**) messages. Here you see the first one.

```
400,t_roll,0.140000,0.000000,0.000000,0.000000
```

Before engaging the platform, the client begins the description of the first sequence, called `t_roll`, using a BEGIN_LONG_SEQ message. The maximum accepted actuator speed is 0.14 metres/second, and the center of rotation is 0.0, 0.0, 0.0.

```
401,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.200000,0.000000,0.000000,0.000000,10.000000,S  
...
```

This is the first LONG_SEQ_STEP message to compose the sequence. One message for each step has to be sent.

```
402
```

The client sends a COMPLETE_LONG_SEQ message, indicating that the sequence is complete.

```
779,403,t_roll,4
```

The server confirms that the sequence has been received and validated, by sending a LONG_SEQ_ACK message. The message informs that the sequence was 4 steps long.

```
400,t_pitch,0.140000,0.000000,0.000000,0.000000
401,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.200000,0.000000,0.000000,0.000000,3.000000,S
...
402
```

The client repeats the steps to define a second sequence, this time called `t_pitch`. One `BEGIN_LONG_SEQ` message, one or more `LONG_SEQ_STEP` or `LONG_SEQ_STEP_SINEACC` messages and one `LONG_SEQ_ACK` message are sent.

```
842,403,t_pitch,4
```

The server confirms that this second sequence has also been received, by sending another `LONG_SEQ_ACK` message. Here, further sequences may be defined. Eventually:

```
3
```

The client sends an `ENGAGE` request.

```
1108,4
```

The server confirms that the engaging request was successfully sent to the Moog platform (`ENGAGE_ACK`). The platform will be engaged, and then it will be brought to the requested operating height.

```
11946,405
11946,6
```

After some time, the server confirms that engage process has been completed by sending first a `LONG_SEQ_AT_HEIGHT` message, and then an `ENGAGE_DONE` message.

```
406,t_roll
```

At this point, the client can play back registered sequences. First, message `LONG_SEQ_AT_START` is sent for sequence `t_roll`.

```
21959,407,t_roll
```

After moving to the position specified as first step of the sequence, the server sends a `LONG_SEQ_READY` message.

```
408
```

At this point, the client can request the playback of the rest of the sequence, by sending message `LONG_SEQ_EXECUTE`.

```
33976,410,t_roll
```

Eventually, the server replies with a `LONG_SEQ_DONE` message, mentioning once more the sequence name.

```
406,t_pitch
```

This time, the client uses message `LONG_SEQ_AT_START` to require playback of sequence `t_pitch`.

```
36992,407,t_pitch
```

Positioning at beginning of the sequence is confirmed.

408

Again, the client requests to the server to execute the rest of the sequence.

49007,410,t_pitch

Eventually, the server confirms the completion of the sequence.

These steps may be repeated as often as needed, for running sequences in order.

7

Eventually, the client requests that the Moog platform initiate a parking sequence (PARK).

109152,8

The server confirms that the park request has been received (PARK_ACK).

117097,10

The server communicates that the parking process has been completed (PARK_DONE).

11,100,carlo.prelz@humdek.unibe.ch,matthias.ertl@psy.unibe.ch

The client requests to close the session (message LOGOUT). Two users will receive messages with post-production results, that will be generated with a 100 millisecond step.

125739,12

The server confirms with a LOGOUT_ACK message before definitively closing the session.

3.8 Immediate session example

This commented example shows what conversation has to take place if one has to run an immediate session.

0,1,37422,0.050000,0.017453,-0.200000

In the login request, type **1** indicates an immediate run. Three compulsory parameters follow:

- 0.050000: The maximum displacement to be accepted between the current and the requested position along any of the three axes (in meters).
- 0.017453 The maximum angular displacement to be accepted between the current and the requested position along any of the three axes (in radians).
- -0.200000 At what height the platform should be positioned before the server begins to accept immediate commands (in meters, *NEGATIVE* upwards, with 0 correspondent to the position of the platform in parked space).

1024,1,190823.082647

Opening is acknowledged. Session begin time is this time August, 23rd, at 08:26:47.

21,100,0,2,0,0.000001,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.000000,-0.000001,0.000000

As shown above, once the session is open, the server starts sending its STATE (**100**) messages. Here you see a sample one.

3

The client sends an ENGAGE request.

2094,4

The server confirms that the engaging request was successfully sent to the Moog platform (ENGAGE_ACK).

14235,203

The server sends out an IMMEDIATE_AT_HEIGHT message, informing that the platform has been positioned at the requested height

14235,6

At the same time, the server confirms that engage process has been completed by sending an ENGAGE_DONE message.

200,0,-0.000000,0.000000,-0.100000,0.000000,0.000000,-0.000000

The client sends the first IMMEDIATE_REQ message requesting an immediate positioning.

The expected parameters are a numeric value to be chosen by the client, possibly representing a progressive count, plus The six DOF values, which are in the same order and with the same convention as used by the Moog platform to report its status:

1. **ROLL** (in radians)
2. **PITCH** (in radians)
3. **heave** (in metres, positive downwards)
4. **surge** (in metres, positive towards the platform)
5. **YAW** (in radians)
6. **lateral** (in metres, positive rightwards)

17200,201,0

The platform replies with an IMMEDIATE_ACK message, quoting the numeric value that was provided by the client. This loop can be repeated as many times as needed.

7

Eventually, the client requests that the Moog platform initiate a parking sequence (PARK).

28861,8

The server confirms that the park request has been received (PARK_ACK).

35327,10

The server communicates that the parking process has been completed (PARK_DONE).

11

The client requests to close the session (message LOGOUT).

35338,12

The server confirms with a LOGOUT_ACK message before definitively closing the session.

3.9 Hardware input messages

The messages described in this section manage the data exchange of the client with the hardware data input devices described in Sec. 2.5.

3.9.1 ACTIVATE_HW_INPUT (22, client to server)

The client requests to the server to be connected to any subset of the existing devices.

The message must contain one comma-separated parameter for each of the hardware devices that access is requested to.

Each parameter will be composed of two or more pipe-separated (|) elements:

- A unique name for the device.
- The tag defining the specific device:
 - `gamepad`: A *playstation gamepad*.
 - `spnav`: A *3Dconnexion Space Navigator*.
 - `xsense`: An *Xsens MTx-series* motion tracker
- For types `gamepad` and `spnav`: any combination of buttons available for the device. Fig. 3.1 shows the tags of the available gamepad buttons, while Tab. 3.7 lists the available buttons of the space navigator device.

Tag	Description
<code>left</code>	Button on the left side of the device.
<code>right</code>	Button on the right side of the device.

Table 3.7: Button tags available for the `spnav` device

Example:

```
22,i1|gamepad|circle,i2|spnav|left|right,i3|xsense
```


Figure 3.1: Button tags available for the gamepad device

3.9.2 HW_INPUT_ACK (23, server to client)

The system communicates that the startup of the hardware input device mechanism has been successfully completed.

Example:

```
12345,23
```

3.9.3 HW_INPUT_NAK (24, server to client)

The system communicates that problems were encountered when dealing with the startup of the hardware input device mechanism.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A short description of the reason of the failure.

Example:

```
12345,24,"new_hw_snav: Device SpaceNavigator not found"
```

3.9.4 HW_INPUT_EVENT (25, server to client)

The server communicates that an event that is of interest of the client has taken place.

As of now, only the state change of buttons is communicated.

The message will contain six parameters:

- The time (in milliseconds since the beginning of the session) when the event was received from the system. This will always be a few milliseconds earlier than the message stamp.
- The name of the device, as passed by the client in message ACTIVATE_HW_INPUT.
- The string BTN.
- The tag of the button that this event refers to.
- 1 if the button has been pressed, 0 if it has been released.

Example:

```
12345,25,12322,i1,BTN,circle,1
```

3.10 Stimuli messages - Audio

3.10.1 AV_AUDIO_ACK (600, server to client)

The system communicates that a request in relation to the audio stimuli mechanism has been successfully completed.

Example:

```
12345,600
```

3.10.2 AV_AUDIO_NAK (601, server to client)

The system communicates that problems were encountered when dealing with a request in relation to the audio stimuli mechanism.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A short description of the reason of the failure.

Example:

```
12345,601,"Error playing sample.raw"
```

3.10.3 AV_OPEN_AUDIO (602, client to server)

The client requests to the server to open its pre-defined audio output. This message must be used in any session, before playing back audio stimuli.

The message must contain one parameter:

- The number of available independent channels to be played in parallel (max. 15).

Example:

```
602,5
```

3.10.4 AV_AUDIO_PLAY (603, client to server)

The client requires the playback of one audio stimulus to one channel. If another stimulus is currently being played back on the same channel, the previous playback is interrupted.

Four parameters are required:

- The name of the audio file, *without the .raw extension*.
- The channel number, starting with **0**.
- The volume to use for the sample, expressed as a floating-point number from **0.0** to **1.0**.
- The number of repetitions of the sample:
 - **0**: play only once.
 - A positive number: repeat the playback of the sample that number of times after the first one (e.g.: if you pass **3**, the sample will be played back for a total of 4 times).
 - A negative number: repeat the sample forever (or until a new sample is submitted, or an AV_AUDIO_STOP message is received, for the channel).

If the requested sample does not exist, an AV_AUDIO_NAK message will be returned, but if the playback of a sample is underway on the given channel, *it will be interrupted* just the same.

The volume value may be kept to **1.0** when no sample overlays are expected to happen. Otherwise, a lower number should be used (e.g. **0.6**) in order to avoid overload and clipping.

Example:

```
603,cowbell,2,0.6,0
```

3.10.5 AV_AUDIO_STOP (604, client to server)

The client asks the server to stop the audio playback on a given channel.

One parameter is required:

- The channel number, starting with 0.

Example:

```
604,2
```

3.10.6 AV_AUDIO_STOP_ALL (605, client to server)

The client asks the server to stop the audio playback on all channels.

Example:

```
605
```

3.10.7 AV_AUDIO_SAMPLE_ENDED (606, server to client)

The server informs the client that the playback of the current sample has completed on a given channel.

The message will contain two parameters:

- The channel number
- The timestamp (in milliseconds after the session start) of the completion of playback.

Example:

```
12345,606,4,12341
```

This message marks the *completed playback* of a sample. No message will be generated when the playback is interrupted due to the start of a new sample on the same channel.

3.11 Stimuli messages - Stills

This stimuli subsystem is intended to show images on various screens located in virtual 3d space, displayed on one or more windows and/or on the screen of a connected HTC Vive visor.

3.11.1 AV_STILLS_ACK (620, server to client)

The system communicates that a request in relation to the still-frame video stimuli mechanism has been successfully completed.

Example:

```
12345,620
```

3.11.2 AV_STILLS_NAK (621, server to client)

The system communicates that problems were encountered when dealing with a request in relation to the still-frame video stimuli mechanism.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A short description of the reason of the failure.

Example:

```
12345,621,"Must send screen number"
```

3.11.3 AV_OPEN_STILLS (622, client to server)

The client requests to the server to start an OpenGL server that will manage one or more windows on the computer screen, and/or the stereo screen of a connected HTC Vive visor.

The server will display on each window, and eventually on the visor screen, one or more virtual screens positioned in 3-D space, that can contain visual stimuli (images). Please refer to Sect. 2.6.2 for more details about the terminology.

This message must be used in any session, before requesting the display of still images.

The message must contain five parameters:

- The X resolution of the still images to be used
- The Y resolution of the still images to be used
- The vertical field-of-view angle to be used in the virtual camera models in place for each screen, in *radians*.
- A string describing what display surfaces will be used.
- A string describing the size and location of the virtual surfaces that will be created.

Please note that the X and Y resolution values are **NOT** used for spherical display surfaces. In those cases, the surface includes the complete 360 degrees horizontal and 180 degrees vertical field of view, and resolution is dynamically changed as needed.

Display surfaces

The parameter that describes the display surfaces to open is composed of sub-parameters separated by a “pipe” character (|). Each subparameter defines one surface, which can be of two types:

- String **VIVE** or **VIVEPRO**, to indicate the usage of a **HTC Vive** or **HTC Vive Pro** virtual reality visor (see Sect. 2.7 for more information).
- Four **integer** numbers separated by a “hash” character (**#**), indicating the offset in pixels, horizontal and vertical, where the window will be displayed on-screen, and its size in pixels (width and height).

At most one visor has to be specified.

Virtual screens

The parameter that describes the virtual screens is composed of sub-parameters separated by a “pipe” character (|). Each subparameter defines one screen.

Screens can be **flat** or **spherical**.

Flat virtual screens

The subparameter for a flat virtual screen is composed of nine “hash” (**#**)-separated **floating-point** fields:

- 1: the letter **F**.
- 2 to 4: the position of the center of the screen in virtual space (x, y and z).
- 5 to 7: the rotation of the screen in space (yaw, pitch and roll) in radians¹.
- 8 and 9: the width and height of the screen.

¹Screens are oriented as flat on the floor as default.

Important tip: It is up to you to make sure that the virtual surfaces you create have the same proportion of the stills being displayed. If, for example, your stills have a proportion of 1024x768 (i.e. 4:3), your screens' width and height must have the same proportion for the images to appear to have the correct proportion.

The user must make sure that the directory for the images relating to the chosen resolution exists (i.e. /moog_base/stills/1024x768/) and that the images that are needed have been generated for that resolution. See Sect. 2.6.2.

Spherical virtual screens

The subparameter for a spherical virtual screen is composed of five "hash" (#)-separated **floating-point** fields:

- 1: the type of the screen.
 - the string **SI** for a screen that displays material on the *internal* surface of the screen.
 - the string **SE** for a screen that displays material on the *external* surface of the screen.
- 2 to 4: the position of the center of the screen in virtual space (x, y and z).
- 5: the radius of the sphere.

Important tip: In the case of spherical screens, the dimensions of the frame are automatically adapted to the screen, filling up the whole surface.

Example

Here is an example string for a command that requires that both a VR visor and a window screen be created, and that one flat and one spherical screen be created:

```
622,600,600,0.43633,VIVE|0#0#1280#1024,F#-500.0#0.0#-1500.0#0.0#1.5707963267948966#0.0#2000.0#2000.0|SE#500.0#0.0#-1500.0#800.0
```

3.11.4 AV_STILLS_STILL (623, client to server)

The client requires the display of one still image onto one of then available screens.

Two parameters are required:

- The name of the still image.
- The progressive number of the screen on which the image has to be displayed.

Example:

```
623,MACCHININA,0
```

3.11.5 AV_STILLS_FILL_RGB (624, client to server)

The client requests to the server to fill one of the still-frame screens with a uniform color.

Four parameters are required:

- The red component of the color (from 0 to 255)
- The green component of the color (from 0 to 255)
- The blue component of the color (from 0 to 255)
- The progressive number of the screen that has to be filled up with the given color.

Example:

```
624,12,24,255,1
```

3.11.6 AV_STILLS_ACTIVATE (625, client to server)

The client requests to the server to display one of the available virtual screens.

```
625,0
```

3.11.7 AV_STILLS_DEACTIVATE (626, client to server)

The client requests to the server **not** to display one of the available virtual screens.

```
626,1
```

3.11.8 AV_STILLS_GET_IPD (627, client to server)

After a “stills” stimuli subsystem has been opened, the OpenGL server is requested to return the current value of interpupillary distance used by the head-mounted display, in case one of these was required. The value will be returned with a subsequent AV_STILLS_IPD_VAL message (see Sec. 3.11.10).

Example:

```
627
```

3.11.9 AV_STILLS_SET_IPD (628, client to server)

After a “stills” stimuli subsystem has been opened, the OpenGL server is requested to adopt the passed value as interpupillary distance for the head-mounted display, if one has been requested.

ONE parameter has to be specified:

- The new interpupillary distance in millimetres.

Example:

```
628,120.01023
```

3.11.10 AV_STILLS_IPD_VAL (629, server to client)

After a “stills” stimuli subsystem has been opened, the OpenGL server returns, upon request, the current value of interpupillary distance used by the head-mounted display, provided one has been requested.

The message includes one parameter:

- The interpupillary distance in millimetres.

Example:

```
12345,629,120.3454
```

3.11.11 AV_STILLS_ROTATE_SCREEN (630, client to server)

The client requires the arbitrary rotation of one of the available screens around its center. Of course, the selected screen has to be of the spherical type, otherwise the command will be rejected.

Three parameters are required:

- The progressive number of the screen.
- The requested, absolute *yaw* angle.
- The requested, absolute *pitch* angle.
- The requested, absolute *roll* angle.

The three angles must be expressed *in radians*.

Example:

```
630,1,0.012,0.2127,1.8
```

3.12 Stimuli messages - Movies

3.12.1 AV_MOVIES_ACK (660, server to client)

The system communicates that a request in relation to the movie video stimuli mechanism has been successfully completed.

Example:

```
12345,660
```

3.12.2 AV_MOVIES_NAK (661, server to client)

The system communicates that problems were encountered when dealing with a request in relation to the movie video stimuli mechanism.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A short description of the reason of the failure.

Example:

```
12345,661,"Player already open"
```

3.12.3 AV_OPEN_MOVIES (662, client to server)

The client requests to the server to start an OpenGL server that will manage one or more windows on the computer screen, and/or the stereo screen of a connected HTC Vive visor.

This message shares the same syntax with message AV_OPEN_STILLS. See Sect. 3.11.3 for the details. In this case, the `ffmpeg` libraries takes care to adapt any movie resolution to the display virtual screens. When using flat virtual screens, you should take care that all displayed movies have the same screen ratio, and that the screens match that ratio (e.g. 4:3, 16:9, etc.).

3.12.4 AV_MOVIES_MOVIE (663, client to server)

The client requires the display of one movie onto one of then available screens.

Four parameters are required:

- The name of the movie.
- The progressive number of the screen on which the image has to be displayed.
- A flag that indicates whether the movie has to be looped. `1` indicates a continuous loop, while `0` indicates that the playback of the movie will terminate at the end (leaving the last frame visible).
- An override flag. `1` indicates that the new movie will substitute the current one in playback (if a movie was playing). `0` indicates that, if a playback is already underway, **the request will be discarded**.

Example:

```
663,passeggiata,0,1,1
```

3.12.5 AV_MOVIES_ROTATE_SCREEN (664, client to server)

The client requires the arbitrary rotation of one of the available screens around its center. Of course, the selected screen has to be of the spherical type, otherwise the command will be rejected.

Three parameters are required:

- The progressive number of the screen.
- The requested, absolute *yaw* angle.
- The requested, absolute *pitch* angle.
- The requested, absolute *roll* angle.

The three angles must be expressed *in radians*.

Example:

```
664,1,0.012,0.2127,1.8
```

3.12.6 AV_MOVIES_PAUSE (665, client to server)

The client requires to the server to either pause or resume playback.

One parameter is required:

- A flag indicating the required action. **1** means *pause*, while **0** means *resume*.

Example:

```
665,0
```

3.12.7 AV_MOVIES_FILL_RGB (624, client to server)

The client requests to the server to fill one of the movie screens with a uniform color.

Four parameters are required:

- The red component of the color (from 0 to 255)
- The green component of the color (from 0 to 255)
- The blue component of the color (from 0 to 255)
- The progressive number of the screen that has to be filled up with the given color.

Example:

```
666,12,24,255,1
```

3.12.8 AV_MOVIES_GET_IPD (667, client to server)

After a movie stimuli subsystem has been opened, the OpenGL server is requested to return the current value of interpupillary distance used by the head-mounted display, in case one of these was required. The value will be returned with a subsequent AV_MOVIES_IPD_VAL message (see Sec. 3.12.10).

Example:

```
667
```

3.12.9 AV_MOVIES_SET_IPD (668, client to server)

After a movie stimuli subsystem has been opened, the OpenGL server is requested to adopt the passed value as interpupillary distance for the head-mounted display, if one has been requested.

ONE parameter has to be specified:

- The new interpupillary distance in millimetres.

Example:

```
668,120.01023
```

3.12.10 AV_MOVIES_IPD_VAL (669, server to client)

After a movie stimuli subsystem has been opened, the OpenGL server returns, upon request, the current value of interpupillary distance used by the head-mounted display, provided one has been requested.

The message includes one parameter:

- The interpupillary distance in millimetres.

Example:

```
12345,669,120.3454
```

3.13 Stimuli messages - Transducer

3.13.1 AV_TRANSD_ACK (640, server to client)

The system communicates that a request in relation to the transducer stimuli mechanism has been successfully completed.

Example:

```
12345,640
```

3.13.2 AV_TRANSD_NAK (641, server to client)

The system communicates that problems were encountered when dealing with a request in relation to the transaction stimuli mechanism.

The message will contain one parameter:

- A short description of the reason of the failure.

Example:

```
12345,641,"Player already open"
```

3.13.3 AV_OPEN_TRANSD (642, client to server)

The client requests to the server to open the transducer server. This message must be used in any session, before requesting the transmission of transducer files

The message must contain four parameters:

- The device type:
 - String `cb_pcimdas` to connect to the DAC hardware to be found in the Moog lab computer.
 - String `TRANS-VIRT` to send data to a virtual DAC device whose output will be visible on-screen (see Fig. 2.7).

- The subdevice number (for the time being, always **1**).
- A string describing the ports to be used. Must be composed of substrings, one for each port to use, separated by a pipe (|) character. Each subpart has to be composed of three elements, separated by a slash (/):
 - The port number (as of now, either **0** or **1** to send data to the real hardware. You can use any number when you use an emulated device).
 - The lower edge of the output signal range, in volt.
 - The higher edge of the output signal range, in volt.
- The frequency at which the samples of the files will be processed (samples per second, floating-number value).

The proposed output signal ranges will be submitted to the kernel subsystem that manages the hardware board. The hardware currently available only allows two ranges:

- From **0.0V** to **5.0V**
- From **0.0V** to **10.0V**

Example:

```
642,cb_pcimdas,1,0/0.0/5.0|6/0.0/10.0,60.0
```

3.13.4 AV_TRANSD_PLAY (643, client to server)

The client requires the transmission of one file to one DAC channel. If another stimulus is currently being transmitted on the same channel, the previous playback is interrupted.

Four parameters are required:

- The channel number.
- The name of the file.
- An indicator of whether the file transmission has to be queued (**0**) or has to interrupt the previous file (**1**)
- The number of repetitions of the sample:
 - **0**: play only once.
 - A positive number: repeat the transmission of the file's contents that number of times after the first one (e.g.: if you pass **3**, the content will be played back for a total of 4 times).
 - A negative number: repeat the transmission forever (or until a new file is submitted, or an AV_TRANSD_STOP message is received, for the channel).

Important tip: When you request the interruption of the previous transmission, this request will only affect the previous element in the queue. If for that element you had not requested the interruption, the element below that in the queue will be transmitted until the end.

If you wish to clean up the queue, use the AV_TRANSD_STOP message.

If the requested file does not exist, an AV_TRANSD_NAK message will be generated, and the request will not be queued. Thus, *it will not interrupt the current transmission, in case one were to be underway.*

Example:

```
643,0,adrh10,1,-1
```

3.13.5 AV_TRANSD_STOP (644, client to server)

The client asks the server to stop the transducer transmission on a given channel.

One parameter is required:

- The channel number.

Example:

```
644,1
```

3.13.6 AV_TRANSD_CHANNEL_IDLE (645, server to client)

The server informs the client that one of the channels has transitioned from a *transmitting* to an *idle* state - i.e. that a channel has exhausted its playback queue.

The message will contain one parameter:

- The channel number

Example:

```
12345,645,1
```

3.14 Stimuli messages - common

3.14.1 AV_INQUIRE (680, client to server)

The client inquires about the existence of a stimulus with a given name.

Two parameters are required:

- One letter indicating the category of the stimulus:
 - 'A': An audio stimulus
 - 'S': A still-image stimulus
 - 'M': A movie stimulus
 - 'T': A transducer stimulus
- The name of the stimulus.

Example:

```
680,A,beam.wav
```

3.14.2 AV_INQUIRE_REPLY (681, server to client)

The server replies to an inquire from the client about the existence of a stimulus.

If problems were encountered the message will include a string with a short description of the causes of the error.

Example:

```
12345,681,"Audio request sent, but audio player not started"
```

Otherwise, three parameters will be found in the reply:

- The category of the stimulus, equal to what was included in the inquire message.
- The name of the stimulus, equal to what was included in the inquire message.
- A number: 1 means that the stimulus exists. 0 means that it does not exist.

Example:

```
12345,681,A,beam.wav,1
```

Chapter 4

julia usage

I have been asked to help in providing the possibility to design and develop clients of the protocol described in this document, using the `julia` language¹.

A warning to the reader is due. This is my first exposure to this language - my first exposure to any so-called functional language as described in https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Functional_programming.

My intention was to set up a skeleton from which other users could benefit, adapting it to specific experiments. I especially wished to encapsulate the networking conversation part into some `julia` code that could be more-or-less copied and pasted.

Originally, I planned to make use of the provided socket library. I was negatively impressed by it, when discovering that the UDP message reading function was not provided with a flag to make it non-blocking. I was then certainly disappointed when reading that I would not really need what was missing in `julia` and is generally present in other socket implementation.

Since I also learned that real threads were also missing from the language implementation, I decided to write short C code to provide a thread that would be responsible for the conversation with the Moog server, in both direction. It would run in its own thread, and would, when requested, send messages to the moog server. Furthermore, it would read all incoming messages and queue them for the client to read them whenever possible, and act accordingly.

The ability of `julia` to execute external C code is, although quite unelegant, simple to implement, and it works smoothly.

In order for this solution to be accepted, I had to make sure that it would work under Linux, Mac and Windows. I created four makefiles, to build these four binary files:

- `moogskt.so` - for Linux. Built under Linux using `Makefile`.
- `moogskt.dlsys` - for Mac. Built under Mac using `Makefile.mac`.
- `moogskt.dll` - 32-bit for windows. Cross-built from my development machine using `Makefile.w`, and added to the repository.
- `moogskt_64.dll` - 64-bit for windows. Cross-built from my development machine using `Makefile.w64`, and added to the repository.

I then wrote some `julia` code in a package. The package can be found in

```
.../julia/MOOG
```

and the actual code is located in

```
.../julia/MOOG/src/MOOG.jl
```

¹<https://julialang.org>

4.1 Preliminary requirements

A few steps must be performed in order to have your Julia scripts able to talk to the Moog platform server.

4.1.1 Linux

1. Install a version of `julia`. I have tried the latest one available on the Git repository (1.4.0-DEV.71), the current stable release (1.2.0) and the version currently distributed by Debian (1.0.4, if I am not mistaken). Test it by verifying that the so-called *REPL* works. When typing

```
julia
```

the interpreter should reply with something similar to this:

```
 _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ | Documentation: https://docs.julialang.org
( ) | ( ) ( ) |
 _ _ _ _ | | _ _ _ _ | Type "?" for help, "]"? for Pkg help.
| | | | | | | | / _ ` | |
| | | | | | | | ( | | | | Version 1.4.0-DEV.71 (2019-08-29)
_ / | _ _ ' | _ | _ | _ _ ' | | Commit 4bf946a9ca (7 days old master)
| _ / | | | | | | | | | | | |
julia>
```

2. You will have to inform `julia` that it can find packages in the directory where you have cloned the repository. You will want to add to your `.profile` file a line like this one:

```
export JULIA_LOAD_PATH='<your-download-path>/MOO-c-interface/julia:$JULIA_LOAD_PATH'
```

If this is successful, typing the command

```
using MOOG
```

at the *REPL* prompt will not generate an error.

3. You will have to generate the dynamic library to be used by your installation. From the `MOO-c-interface` directory, execute this command:

```
(cd julia/c && make)
```

and you should find a new file called `moogskt.so` under `julia/c`. If this is successful, from the *REPL* prompt you should be able to write these two lines:

```
using MOOG
ccall((:moogskt_init,MOOG.MOOGSKT_C_MODULE), Cint, (Cstring,Cstring,Cint,Cint),
      "<your--ip-address>",
      MOOG.SERVER_MOOG_ADDRESS,MOOG.SERVER_OUTPORT,MOOG.SERVER_INPORT)
```

The C code should notify that it has been activated by printing on your screen a line like this one:

```
[190905.150421] Moogskt begin loop
```

4. At this time you should be able to run a `julia` script similar to the one to be found at `julia/3.jl`. Just remember to modify the field with your IP address.

4.1.2 Apple Macintosh

The procedure is similar. You only have to use this line to compile the C code:

```
(cd julia/c && make -f Makefile.mac)
```

4.1.3 windows

Someone has been able to run a `julia` script that made use of my socket/thread code under windows in my presence. The effort has been made under a 64-bit version of **windows 7**. Other versions would need to be tested independently.

These steps needed to be performed (all performed by the system administrator):

- A pre-compiled version of `julia` had to be installed. This has not been done in my presence, but I assume that that was sufficiently straightforward. The version of the language was 1.2.0. A terminal with the usual `julia` REPL prompt appeared when double-clicking the icon.
- The ethernet port of the windows machine had to be configured to a fixed address, to be able to talk to the Moog machine via the switch.
- A copy of the `MOO-standalone` project was saved in the main disk of the windows machine. Its path was:

```
C:\Users\admin\Documents\juliastuff\pro\MOO_Standalone
```

- Inside `julia/MOOG/src/MOOG.jl`, the line defining constant `MOOGSKT_C_MODULE` had to be modified as follows²:

```
const  
↳ MOOGSKT_C_MODULE="C:\\Users\\admin\\Documents\\juliastuff\\pro\\MOO_Standalone\\julia\\c\\moogskt_64"
```

- I added to the test script I used to try the mechanism (`4b.jl`), *before the `Using` line*, this line:

```
push!(LOAD_PATH, "C:\\Users\\admin\\Documents\\juliastuff\\pro\\MOO_Standalone\\julia")
```

This line has the same effect as adding the path where the `julia` modules are contained into environment variable `JULIA_LOAD_PATH` (I followed this second strategy in the Linux and Mac cases).

I also modified the line in that script where the client address is stored:

```
address="192.168.1.204"
```

At this point, I was able to successfully execute the test script, which logged into the Moog server and performed the tasks required by the script.

²Note that the last part of the path reads `moogskt_64`, indicating that the 64-bit version of the DLL was used

Part II

Special research projects

This section contains details about ad-hoc code developed for specific research projects. The projects define higher-level operations to be executed from the Ruby master process, interacting with both the Moog platform and other hardware or libraries accessible by the Ruby interpreter.

Chapter 5

“Efference”

5.1 Theory

This project interfaces with:

- the Moog platform
- the HTC Vive visor
- the OpenGL graphical subsystem.

in order to estimate the ability of human beings to remember motion amplitudes when efference copy is or is not present.

The interface has been designed to permit the execution of five types of tests. In all types, the subject has to deal with three or four objects emulated in virtual space and displayed on the Vive visor:

- A sphere that is fixed in objective space, in front of the subject.
- A sphere that is fixed in objective space, rotated at a given angle around the vertical (yaw) and horizontal (pitch) axes.
- A sphere that is fixed in **subjective** space, in front of the subject (i.e. it always remains in front of the subject, no matter how his/her head is rotated).
- If needed, a sphere that is meant as a guide, to indicate to the subject the proper speed of rotation when s/he has to perform an active or decoupled motion.

Pitch	Max. yaw
-14°	1°
-13°	2°
-12°	3°
-11°	4°
-10°	5°
-9°	7°
-8°	8°
-7°	9°
-6°	11°
-5°	12°
-4°	14°
-3°	15°
-2°	17°
-1°	19°
0°	21°
1°	20°
2°	19°
3°	17°
4°	16°
5°	15°
6°	14°
7°	13°
8°	12°
9°	11°
10°	10°
11°	10°
12°	9°
13°	8°
14°	7°
15°	5°
16°	4°
17°	3°
18°	1°

Table 5.1: Yaw/pitch ranges

The yaw and pitch angles at which the *rotated* sphere may be placed is limited by the platform's range of possible motion. **No matter what type of test is being performed, the proposed rotation is always validated against the reach of the platform**, even if the platform will not move at all. Table 5.1 indicates the available yaw range (absolute value) for each degree of pitch that is reachable (values in sexagesimal degrees).

The values refer to a platform set to a height of **-0.199m**. This value is chosen as the operative height for sessions of this type, because it allows the maximum possible yaw rotation with no pitch rotation (about 21°).

The goal of the tests is to move the subjectively-fixed sphere so that it first covers the one at the side, and then returns to cover the one in front of the subject. This may happen in five ways:

- The subject actually rotates his/her head to reach the target and back (*ACTIVE* test).
- The subject actually rotates his/her head to reach the target and back, while trying to follow the pace suggested by a moving guide (*GUIDED* test).
- The subject actually rotates his/her head to reach the target and back, while trying to follow the pace suggested by a moving guide; at the same time the Moog platform rotates at a possibly different angle (*DECOUPLED* test).

- The Moog platform on which the subject is sitting rotates to align the subject with the rotated sphere (*PASSIVE* test).
- No rotation actually takes place: the subject only **thinks** about reaching the rotated sphere (*IMAGINATIVE* test).

At any moment, instead of a test, the subject may be asked to replicate the range of the preceding rotation from memory, trying to match its extension and confirming the choice by pressing a button on the gamepad.

In the case of a test making use of the accessory guiding ball (*GUIDED* or *DECOUPLED*), the ACK message generated at the end of the test will contain eight values (all expressed in sexagesimal degrees):

- The maximum (absolute) yaw error that the subject had from the guide during the *forward* step.
- The average (absolute) yaw error that the subject had from the guide during the *forward* step.
- The maximum (absolute) pitch error that the subject had from the guide during the *forward* step.
- The average (absolute) pitch error that the subject had from the guide during the *forward* step.
- The maximum (absolute) yaw error that the subject had from the guide during the *backward* step.
- The average (absolute) yaw error that the subject had from the guide during the *backward* step.
- The maximum (absolute) pitch error that the subject had from the guide during the *backward* step.
- The average (absolute) pitch error that the subject had from the guide during the *backward* step.

Tests are composed of these steps:

- **Center:** the subject aligns the head with the current reference orientation.
- **Forward:** The motion towards the rotated sphere takes place.
- **Backward:** The motion back to the front sphere takes place.

5.1.1 Motion interpolation

From the onset of this project, it was decided to interpolate all motions, either physical or guiding, by applying De Casteljau's algorithm, imposing 1st (velocity) and 2nd (acceleration) derivatives to 0 at both beginning and end (see Sect. 1.3.3). At a later time, request was made to give the possibility to use other forms of interpolation - specifically, to have the motion of **tests** be governed by a damped harmonic oscillation (see Sect. 1.3.5) (of course, simple motions still use De Casteljau's algorithm).

This possibility has been added. It is available for all modes **except for *DECOUPLED* mode**. This is because the times of execution of damped harmonic oscillation motions are difficult to pinpoint, and allowing for the possibility to have two different oscillation motions, one for the platform and the other for the guiding ball, and constraining them to last the same time posed problems that it was decided were not worth solving.

Obviously, the type of motion is irrelevant for *IMAGINATIVE* and *ACTIVE* tests. It is only relevant for:

- *PASSIVE* tests: the algorithm dictates how the platform will move.
- *GUIDED* tests: the algorithm dictates how the guiding ball will move.
- *DECOUPLED* tests: the algorithm dictates how both the platform and the guiding ball will move; only De Casteljau's algorithm can be selected.

5.2 Session initiation

The session is initiated by sending to the server a LOGIN message requesting the start of a session of type **5**.

Example:

```
0,5,6211,VIVEPRO,1.5,0.05,024008,0.045,701008,0.055,504010,0.02,0.25,102050,0.4,0.01,550000,005500,000055,441100,3355AA,55.0,20111
```

Here is a description of the parameters used in the login message:

- Pos. 1: LOGIN command (**0**)
- Pos. 2: Session type (**5**, see Table 3.2)
- Pos. 3: UDP port to be contacted from (e.g. **6211**, see 3.4.10)
- Pos. 4: The type of visor to be used (**VIVE** for the HTC Vive, **VIVEPRO** for the HTC Vive Pro).
- Pos. 5: Distance in virtual space of the various spheres from the subject (**1.5**)
- Pos. 6, 7: diameter and RGB color of the *fixed* sphere (**0.05,024008**)
- Pos. 8, 9: diameter and RGB color of the sphere *in front* (**0.045,701008**)
- Pos. 10, 11: diameter and RGB color of the *rotated* sphere (**0.055,504010**)
- Pos. 12 to 14: diameter, positioning offset along the Z axis¹ and RGB color of the *guiding* sphere (**0.02,0.25,102050**)
- Pos. 15 to 21: details of the reference cross that will appear in front of the subject, to be used by the subject to align his/her head right before starting each test:
 - Pos. 15: the length of the cross arms (**0.4**)
 - Pos. 16: the diameter of the cross arms (**0.01**)
 - Pos. 17: the colour used for the cross before an *ACTIVE* test (**550000**)
 - Pos. 18: the colour used for the cross before a *PASSIVE* test (**005500**)
 - Pos. 19: the colour used for the cross before an *IMAGINATIVE* test (**000055**)
 - Pos. 20: the colour used for the cross before a *GUIDED* test (**441100**)
 - Pos. 21: the colour used for the cross before a *DECOUPLED* test (**3355AA**)
- Pos. 22: The vertical field of view angle, in sexagesimal degrees, to apply to the head-mounted visor (**55.0**).
- Pos. 23: The broadcast UDP port to open to dump the rotational asset of the visor in real time (see Sect. 2.7.1). If a value of 0 or less is passed, no port will be opened (**20111**).

When the session has been successfully opened, the server engages the Moog platform, and positions it to the operative height. It then enters idle mode.

The visor will have to be left still for a few seconds (lying on a solid surface) for it to be operative (the same is required when sending message `EFFE_CALIBRATE_VISOR`)

¹While all the other spheres are positioned at the same distance from the subject (co-planar), this one may be offset from that plane in order to disturb as little as possible the perception of the scene while performing its task. Two strategies may be adopted: either this ball is sensibly smaller than the others, and positioned in front of the other balls (as can be seen in the example), or it is larger and positioned behind the other objects.

5.3 The *run*

After a successful login, four kinds of activities are possible within an “efference” session:

- By sending an `EFFE_TESTMODE_ON` message, the test mode may be entered, that is useful for allowing subjects to practice the interface. This mode is also useful for correctly tuning the interpupillary distance. This mode is left by sending an `EFFE_TESTMODE_OFF` message.
- By sending an `EFFE_EXERCISEMODE_ON` message, the exercise mode may be entered. In this mode, subjects may practice the ability to track moving objects with the motion of their heads. This mode is left by sending an `EFFE_EXERCISEMODE_OFF` message.
- By sending an `EFFE_PARK` message, the server is instructed to cleanly close the session.
- In order to position the platform, perform actual tests and request subject evaluations, a so-called *run* must be opened. *Runs* are opened by sending an `EFFE_BEGIN_RUN` command, and they are closed with command `EFFE_COMPLETE_RUN`.

Runs are identified by names.

Important tip: The server has not much concern with what names you chose for your runs. you are allowed to always reuse the same name. It is in your interest to provide names that are meaningful and unique, so that they can be identified in the data files that you will receive at the end of your sessions.

The idea is that you may always close the current run and start a new one when you want to indicate that conditions in your experiment have changed.

Within a run, the client has the possibility to:

- Set the reference orientation (`EFFE_SAVE_REFERENCE` message, see 5.4.13).
- Define the interpolation parameters that subsequent tests will use (`EFFE_INTERPOL_DATA` message, see 5.4.9).
- Run a test (`EFFE_RUN_TEST` message, see 5.4.12).
- Ask for the performance of an evaluation (`EFFE_EVALUATE` message, see 5.4.4).
- Close the run (`EFFE_COMPLETE_RUN` message, see 5.4.3).

5.4 Client-to-server messages

5.4.1 `EFFE_BEGIN_RUN` (514)

Once an “efference” session is open, this message permits the opening of a named *run*.

ONE parameter has to be specified:

- The name of the *run*.

Example:

```
514, test-run
```

5.4.2 EFFE_CALIBRATE_VISOR (502)

Once an “efference” session is open, when receiving this message, the server will instruct the visor software to initiate a gyroscope calibration.

As a consequence, the background of the visor and reference screens will become red, and the updating of the virtual 3d world will be suspended until the visor has been still for a sufficient time, and a new gyroscope reading corresponding to the non-moving condition has been recorded.

When the process is complete, the background of the visor and reference screens will return to black, and the client will receive an EFFE_VISOR_CALIBRATED message.

The process that is started when receiving this message includes the updating of the center reference, as if message EFFE_SAVE_REFERENCE had been received.

Example:

```
502
```

5.4.3 EFFE_COMPLETE_RUN (518)

While running an “efference” session, this messages requires the server to properly close the *run* that is currently underway.

Example:

```
518
```

5.4.4 EFFE_EVALUATE (517)

The goal of the “efference” experiment is for the subject to try and evaluate the extension of a previously experienced rotation by rotating his/her head to where the subject thinks its destination was, without any visual stimulus, and pressing a button.

This evaluation can take place when the client sends message EFFE_EVALUATE to the server. The server will allow the subject to rotate his/her head and confirm by pressing a button on the game controller.

When this test is completed, the server will reply by sending an EFFE_ACK message followed by an EFFE_CURR_ANGLE message (see Sect. 5.5.2) including the current orientation of the platform as well as the orientation returned by the VIVE visor’s gyroscope. Example:

```
517
```

5.4.5 EFFE_EXERCISEMODE_ON (505)

The “efference” session has a so-called *exercise* mode. In this mode, the three spheres are made visible, and the *rotated* sphere follows an eight-shaped pattern, that the subject should be encouraged to follow by moving the head.

Figure 5.1: The eight-shaped curve

Also in exercise mode, it will be possible for the client to send `EFFE_SAVE_REFERENCE` messages to match the center orientation of the visor to a neutral head position.

This message causes the session, when in idle state, to enter exercise mode.

Four parameters are required:

- The period (in seconds) that each complete eight-pattern lasts.
- The extension of the pattern in the horizontal direction
- The extension of the pattern in the vertical direction
- The direction of motion: if 1, the motion will be upwards near the center and downwards far from the center. If 0, the reverse will be true.

Example:

```
505,15.0,1600.0,750.0,1
```

5.4.6 EFFE_EXERCISEMODE_OFF (506)

This message causes the session, when in exercise mode, to return to idle state.

Example:

```
506
```

5.4.7 EFFE_GET_CURR_ANGLE (512)

While an “efference” session is underway, if the server receives this message, it will reply with an EFFE_CURR_ANGLE message containing the current Moog platform angle (yaw pitch) - that is, the angle where it was left by the latest POSITION command.

Example:

```
512
```

5.4.8 EFFE_GET_IPD (507)

While an “efference” session is underway, the remote server is requested to return the current value of interpupillary distance used by the head-mounted display. The value will be returned with a subsequent EFFE_IPD_VAL message (see Sect. 5.5.3).

Example:

```
507
```

5.4.9 EFFE_INTERPOL_DATA (520)

Before any “efference” test can be run, it is necessary to inform the system about the data that will be used to define the motion of either the platform or the guiding ball.

As described in Sect. 5.1.1, two types of interpolation can be requested. The beginning parameters are common for both types:

- (1, 2) The angle (yaw and pitch) that has to be reached in test using this interpolation data, in radians.
- (3) The amount of uninterrupted time that must pass with the subjective and objective spheres sufficiently near to each other for any of the various steps of the test to be considered complete.
- (4) The maximum distance between the centers of the two spheres to consider them to be sufficiently near to each other.
- (5, 6) A further offset angle (yaw and pitch) that has to be added to the positions of all the objects that will appear in the virtual world, which will impose to the subject a further (constant) torsion of the neck to match its view with the resulting motion.

De Casteljau interpolation

For De Casteljau interpolation, two more parameters are required:

- (7) The letter 'C'
- (8) The speed to adopt for the rotation, in radians/sec.

Example:

```
520,0.174533,-0.087266,1.0,0.05,0.0,0.0,C,0.02
```

Damped harmonic oscillator interpolation

When motion has to follow the behaviour of a damped harmonic oscillator, six more parameters are defined:

- (7) The letter 'O' (an uppercase 'o', **not** a zero)
- (8) The mass of the oscillating object.
- (9) The elasticity constant of the emulated spring.
- (10) The dampening factor.
- (11) The maximum duration time.
- (12) the energy level threshold under which the motion is considered complete.

Please see Sect. 1.3.5 for more details about this interpolating algorithm and the data that define it.

Example:

```
520,0.069813,-0.034907,1.0,0.05,0.0,0.0,0,0.8,2.0,0.7,15.0,0.000020
```

5.4.10 EFFE_PARK (519)

When the client has completed the required tests and closed the latest run, before logging out from the server, it must send to the server this command *instead of using the generic park command*. The parking procedure will proceed as usual, and the client will have to wait for a regular PARK_DONE message before the logout request can be sent.

Example:

```
519
```

5.4.11 EFFE_POSITION (515)

Once an “efference” run is open, it is possible to position the Moog platform at any permissible value of yaw and pitch rotation. The given position, after having been reached, will represent the start position for any test that needs to be run.

The client specifies, together with the desired values of yaw and pitch, the speed at which the displacement is to be performed *in radians/sec*. The speed is used to compute the time that the displacement will last by considering a theoretical displacement at constant speed, while for the actual displacement the **De Casteljau** interpolation (see Sect. 1.3.3) will be used.

Three parameters are required:

- The value of the yaw-rotation component of the destination position in radians.
- The value of the pitch-rotation component of the destination position in radians.
- The desired (average) speed in radians/sec.

Example:

```
515,-0.034907,-0.226893,0.05
```

5.4.12 EFFE_RUN_TEST (516)

Once an “efference” run is open and interpolation data have been defined, it is possible to run an instance of any of the five types of tests² by sending this message.

Tests consist in:

- the matching of a cross with a specific color with the fixed ball, that indicates that the subject is ready for the test.
- a forward rotation to a given yaw/pitch angle
- a backward rotation back to the origin

Tag	Description
ACT	Active test (the subject must move his/her head)
GUI	Guided test (same as Active, but an extra sphere guides the subject by showing what the motion should be)
DEC	Decoupled test (same as Guided, but the Moog platform rotates the subject by a different angle)
PAS	Passive test (the Moog platform will rotate the subject)
IMG	Imaginative test (the subject must imagine that the head rotates)

Table 5.2: “Efference” test types

For all test types, two parameters have to be supplied:

- (1) A string identifying the name of the test. This string is intended as an aid to the designer of the experiment. It won't be used by the server, but it will be included in the post-produced session result files.
- (2) The tag identifying the test type (see Table 5.2).

Important tip: As soon as the server receives this message, the travel between the current platform position and the yaw and pitch parameters defined in the currently active interpolation data is verified for compatibility with the operative limits of the Moog platform (both w.r.t. actuator extensions and speed), *even if the test type does not require any rotation to take place*. This is a design choice, motivated by consistency. It was decided that rotation interpolated data not compatible with the Moog device would be better avoided at all time, and thus they are flagged as errors even if no platform motion is actually required

A few test types require further parameters.

PASSIVE test extra parameters

The PASSIVE test requires one further parameter:

- (3) The time in seconds that the server will pause the platform after the destination is reached and before the platform starts the backward rotation.

IMAGINATIVE test extra parameters

The IMAGINATIVE test will **not** base its timing on the requested rotation angle and speed. The test requires two further parameters:

- (3) The time in seconds that the imagined forward rotation will last.
- (4) The time in seconds that the imagined backward rotation will last.

²Not DECOUPLED when damped harmonic oscillator interpolation has been chosen.

DECOUPLED test extra parameters

The DECOUPLED test will require that the platform be rotated to an angle in space (yaw and pitch) that is unrelated to the angle specified in the currently active interpolation data. The test requires two further parameters:

- (3) The yaw angle to rotate the platform (in radians)
- (4) The pitch angle to rotate the platform (in radians)

This second angle is also verified as per reachability by the platform, as well as speed. The speed is computed so that the platform motion takes the same length of time as the rotation in virtual world specified by the interpolation data.

Examples

- **ACTIVE** test

```
516, t1, ACT
```

- **GUIDED** test

```
516, t2, GUI
```

- **PASSIVE** test

```
516, t3, PAS, 1.5
```

- **IMAGINATIVE** test

```
516, t4, IMG, 1.5, 2.5
```

- **DECOUPLED** test

```
516, t5, DEC, 0.034907, 0.226893
```

5.4.13 EFFE_SAVE_REFERENCE (504)

Once an “efference” session is open, when receiving this message, the master process will consider the current visor orientation as the center reference. Orientation quaternions generated from this moment on will represent an offset from the orientation the visor has when this message was received.

Example:

```
504
```

5.4.14 EFFE_SET_IPD (508)

While an “efference” session is underway, the remote server is requested to adopt the passed value as interpupillary distance for the head-mounted display.

ONE parameter has to be specified:

- The new interpupillary distance in millimetres.

Example:

```
508, 120.01023
```

5.4.15 EFFE_TESTMODE_ON (510)

The “efference” session has a so-called *test* mode. In this mode, the three main spheres are made visible (the *rotated* sphere at the maximum permitted clockwise yaw angle). The subject can make use of this mode to familiarize with the operation of moving the subjectively fixed sphere so that it covers either of the objectively fixed spheres.

It will be possible for the client to send EFFE_SAVE_REFERENCE messages to match the center orientation of the visor to a neutral head position.

This message causes the session, when in idle state, to enter test mode.

Example:

```
510
```

5.4.16 EFFE_TESTMODE_OFF (511)

This message causes the session, when in test mode, to return to idle state.

Example:

```
511
```

5.5 Server-to-client messages

5.5.1 EFFE_ACK (500)

The server acknowledges the success of an operation related to an “efference” session.

This message can be generated in the following situations:

- The opening of a new *run*.
- The success of a positioning.
- The acceptance of a set of interpolation data.
- The completion of a test.
- The completion of an evaluation, before the EFFE_CURR_ANGLE message containing the evaluation data is sent.
- The closing of a run.

The message includes one parameter:

- The numeric identifier of the message that this message is acknowledging.

Example:

```
12345,500.514
```

Guided ball data

When an `EFFE_ACK` message confirms the successful completion of a test that involves the subject's tracking of a guiding ball (*GUIDED* and *DECOUPLED* tests), the message includes eight further data elements with statistical data about the angular distance (in radians) between the subjective and guided balls:

- The average yaw distance during forward motion
- The maximum yaw distance during forward motion
- The average pitch distance during forward motion
- The maximum pitch distance during forward motion
- The average yaw distance during backward motion
- The maximum yaw distance during backward motion
- The average pitch distance during backward motion
- The maximum pitch distance during backward motion

Example:

```
12345,500,516,0.170572,1.559529,0.092222,1.522282,0.173957,1.570690,0.064190,1.518410
```

5.5.2 EFFE_CURR_ANGLE (513)

This message contains four parameters:

- The yaw and pitch of the actual position of the platform, in radians.
- The yaw and pitch of the actual orientation of the visor, in radians.

It can be generated by an “efference” session in two cases:

- When the server has been instructed to execute an evaluation: the message will contain the data relative to the moment when the subject pressed the evaluate button.
- When the server has received an `EFFE_GET_CURR_ANGLE` message from the client.

Example:

```
12345,513,0.070833,-0.214218,0.000000,-1.570451
```

5.5.3 EFFE_IPD_VAL (509)

While an “efference” session is underway, the remote server returns, upon request, the current value of interpupillary distance used by the head-mounted display.

The message includes one parameter:

- The interpupillary distance in millimetres.

Example:

```
12345,509,120.3454
```

5.5.4 EFFE_NAK (501)

The server informs that something has been unsuccessful during an “efference” session.

The message includes one parameter:

- A brief description of the fault being raised.

Example:

```
12345,501,501,"POSITION: destination invalid: Motion failed at 16msec: Too short"
```

5.5.5 EFFE_VISOR_CALIBRATED (503)

The server communicates to the client that the visor calibration process has been completed.

Example:

```
12345,503
```

5.6 Session example

This commented example shows what conversation has to take place if one has to run an “efference” session. As in the previous cases, a *red* tab indicates a message from client to server, and a *green* tab indicates a message from server to client.

```
0,5,8937,VIVEPR0,1.5,0.05,024008,0.045,701008,0.055,504010,0.02,0.25,102050,0.4,0.01,550000,005500,000055,441100,3355aa,55.000000,20111
```

In the login request, type **5** indicates an “efference” run. The parameters are described in Sect. 5.2.

```
5001,1,201019.084523
```

Opening is acknowledged. The session has begun on October, 19th, at 08:45:23

```
29
```

The client requests the name of the current *topic*.

```
5010,30,effe2
```

The server replies with the name of the current *topic*.

Important tip: With the current version of the “efference” project, the server does not ensure anymore that it is running with the appropriate version of the software. Instead, it is the duty of the client to request which *topic* the server is using, and verify that it corresponds with the one that is maintained to run that specific project.

In the case of this example, the server is running *topic* **effe2**, the correct one for the specific circumstances.

```
12500,6
```

In 12.5 seconds, the engagement of the platform is confirmed. **It was not necessary to explicitly request the engagement.** This session type requires the Moog platform to be engaged all the time, thus the relative request is automatically generated by the server.

502

The client requests to re-calibrate the gyroscope data.

13400,503

The server communicates that the visor is now calibrated.

514,run_21

The client asks to open a new *run*, called **run_21**.

13595,500,514

The server acknowledges then opening of the *run*.

515,-0.096308,0.282955,0.100118

The client requests a platform position change.

13715,501,"POSITION: destination invalid: Motion failed at 2483msec: Too long"

The platform cannot position to the requested position, and thus the request is refused.

515,-0.120507,0.089510,0.091862

The client requests a new platform position change, with different parameters.

15876,500,515

The server validated and performed the position change.

520,0.197782,-0.145603,1.0,0.05,0.0,0.0,C,0.073763

The client sends a set of data for a De Casteljau interpolation

15996,500,520

The server confirms the reception

516,DEC_15,DEC,0.128553,-0.225049

The client requests the run of a **DECOUPLED** test.

16161,501,"RUN_TEST destination invalid: Motion failed at 3933msec: Too short"

The platform cannot validate the motion required by the requested test, and thus the request is refused.

■ 520,0.349066,-0.087266,1.0,0.05,0.0,0.0,C,0.02

The client sends a new interpolation data set.

■ 16006,500,520

The server confirms the reception

■ 516,DEC_15,DEC,0.128553,-0.225049

The client repeats the request for the run of a *DECOUPLED* test.

■ 35212,500,516,0.282213,1.544339,0.194040,1.236433,0.428133,1.526704,0.234372,1.305648

This time the server validates and executes the test. At the end the test is acknowledged.

■ 517

The client requests that the subject perform an evaluation

■ 36221,500,517

First of all, the client acknowledges the evaluation request

■ 40323,513,-0.012251,-0.041157,0.000000,-1.570451

As soon as the subject performs the evaluation, the relative data are returned to the client.

■ 520,0.069813,-0.349066,1.0,0.05,0.0,0.0,0,0.8,2.0,0.7,15.0,0.00002

The client sends the data set for a dumped harmonic oscillator interpolation.

■ 41722,500,520

The server confirms the reception

■ 516,PAS_33,PAS,1.5

The client requests the execution of a *PASSIVE* test.

■ 43412,500,516

The server confirms the completion of the test.

■ 518

Eventually, the client closes the *topic*.

■ 44711,500,518

The server acknowledges the closing of the *topic*.

■ 519

The client closes the session by sending to the server the specific “efference” PARK command.

■ 45012,10

The server confirms that parking was completed by sending the standard PARK_DONE message.

■ 11,100

The client logs out, requesting a results file to be produced.

Chapter 6

“Macaco”

6.1 Theory

Here is an academical description of what is being researched with this project:

Neural correlates of optimal multisensory decision making under time-varying reliabilities with an invariant linear probabilistic population code.

From the point of view of the software engineer, this translates to the following:

A number of equilateral triangle of the same size, color and orientation are distributed at random within a given volume in virtual space. The volume is placed in front of the perceiver.

A trial consists in the following:

- A given percentage of the existing triangles move coherently towards the perceiver, for a given distance and at a given **yaw** angle with relation to the line that connects the container block and the observer.
- The rest of the triangles move in a random direction, and for a random distance within a given maximum.
- The subject has to perceive whether the coherent triangles are moving towards his/her right or left.

The subject is sitting on the Moog platform. The platform may or may not move in sync with the block of triangles. Three types of trials result:

- Only the triangles move.
- Only the platform moves. In this case, no triangles are seen by the subject.
- Both the triangles and the platform move.

The parameters for an object to be used as target have to be provided. This object, a coloured cross, remains fixed in space in the background.

The name of the project derives from the fact that this effort is intended to replicate on humans a research already performed on macaques.

Fig. 6.1 shows the triangle area from an off-center point of view. The dark-blue spheres (added in this image to illustrate the resulting geometry) delimit the area where the triangles are randomly distributed. The three arrows in front indicate the cartesian axes (X: red, Y: blue, Z: green).

Figure 6.1: Macaco screenshot

The operative height at which the biggest backwards displacement of the Moog platform is reached is **205mm**. At this height, the platform can move backwards for **221mm**.

From this start position, the platform can move forward for a variable maximum amount, depending from the angle. The limit is plotted in the graph contained in Fig. 6.2. Here is a summary table.

Angle (degrees)	Max. displacement (mm)
0	473
5	451
10	435
15	419
20	405
25	393
30	383
35	353
40	326
45	303
50	284
55	266
60	251
65	241
70	151
75	41

Figure 6.2: Maximum displacement w.r.t. angle

6.1.1 Operative modes

Two modes currently exist for submitting subjects to tests. They can be mixed in a single session. You choose the operative mode by using different commands.

Standard mode

The expression of the subject's perception of the direction of motion is obtained by pressing either one of the two left-side front-facing buttons of the gamepad, or one of the two right-side front-facing buttons of the same. The subject *must* choose one of the two directions. The return path of the platform and/or of the triangles will not begin until one of the permissible gamepad buttons are pressed.

It is selected by using command `MACACO_RUN_TASK` (see Sect. 6.3.4).

Ring mode

Figure 6.3: Macaco: ring mode

In ring mode, the subject is displayed, somewhere within the perceived virtual world, a visual device that will aid in remembering the moment during the movement when the subject perceived the direction of motion.

The device is something analogous to the face of a clock. You can see it, immersed into the bunch of triangles, in Fig. 6.3. It is composed by a torus-shaped *ring*, and a rotating indicator made up of an *arm* and a *tip*.

The indicator will rotate linearly during the forward movement, from an initial position to a final position, both specifiable for each task.

The device will then disappear during the return movement, and will be shown again as soon as the return motion is completed, with the indicator pointing upwards. At this point, the subject will have to complete two tasks, by interfacing with the gamepad:

1. the direction that has been perceived will have to be selected (by pressing any of the two front-facing left or right buttons). A colored arrow-like cone will appear on the selected side within the visual range of the subject. The choice can be overridden as often as needed.
2. The moment in time when the direction has been perceived will have to be communicated, *by replicating on the rotating device the position that the indicator had* at that moment. The indicator can be rotated by pressing the **square** or **circle** buttons on the gamepad (refer to Fig. 3.1).

The selection will have to be confirmed by pressing the **select** button.

This operative mode is selected by using command `MACACO_RUN_TASK_RING` (see Sect. 6.3.5).

6.2 Session initiation

The session is initiated by sending to the server a LOGIN message requesting the start of a session of type 6.

Example:

```
0,6,47476,VIVE,1000.0|1000.0|500.0,1000,10.0,85a32b,0.0|0.0|250.0,2.0|40.0|-1000.0|031025,
0.0|0.0|-150.0|200.0|20.0|204080|606060|e0b020,65.0
```

Here is a description of the parameters used in the login message:

- Pos. 1: LOGIN command (0)
- Pos. 2: Session type (6, see Table 3.2)
- Pos. 3: UDP port to be contacted from (e.g. 47476, see 3.4.10)
- Pos. 4: The type of visor to be used (VIVE for the HTC Vive, VIVEPRO for the HTC Vive Pro).
- Pos. 5: Dimensions of the box that contains the triangles (three floating-point values separated by a pipe character – |) (1000.0|1000.0|500.0)
- Pos. 6: The number of triangles to be generated (1000)
- Pos. 7: The length of the triangle side (10.0)
- Pos. 8: The colour of the triangles (85a32b)
- Pos. 9: The position of the viewpoint of both the camera and the head-mounted display (three floating-point values separated by a pipe character – |) as an offset to the center of the cartesian axes shown in Fig. 6.1 (1000.0|1000.0|500.0)
- Pos. 10: A string containing four pipe (|)-separated fields, defining the properties of the target:
 - The diameter of the arms of the cross (2.0)
 - The size of the cross (two times the arm length) (40.0)
 - The position of the center along the Z axis according to the cartesian space shown in Fig. 6.1 (-1000.0)
 - The colour of the cross (031025)
- Pos. 11: The parameters that describe the ring-mode indicator. If the string is non-empty, it must be made up of eight pipe (|)-separated fields (please refer to Fig. 6.3):
 - 1 to 3: the position in virtual space where the center of the indicator will be located (0.0|0.0|-150.0).
 - 4: the radius of the ring (from the center of the indicator to the center of the torus doughnut) (200.0).
 - 5: the radius of the torus doughnut (20.0).
 - 6: The colour of the ring (204080)
 - 7: The colour of the arm (606060)
 - 8: The colour of the tip (e0b020)
- Pos. 12: The vertical field of view angle, to apply both to the visor and to the on-screen monitor window (65.0).

Important tip: It is legal to pass an empty string for parameter #11 (description of the ring-mode indicator). In this case, an error message will be returned if trying to start a ring-mode task (by using the `MACACO_RUN_TASK_RING` command).

When the session has been successfully opened, the server engages the Moog platform, and positions it to the operative height. It then moves backwards as much as possible, and enters idle mode.

6.3 Client-to-server messages

6.3.1 MACACO_TESTMODE_ON (713)

The “macaco” session has a so-called *test* mode. In this mode, the three spheres are made visible (the *rotated* sphere at the maximum permitted clockwise angle). The subject can make use of this mode to familiarize with the operation of moving the subjectively fixed sphere so that it covers either of ten objectively fixed spheres.

When in test mode, it will be possible for the subject under test to make use of the gamepad buttons to finely tune the visor’s inter-pupillary distance (**IPD**).

This message causes the session, when in idle state, to enter test mode.

Example:

```
501
```

6.3.2 MACACO_TESTMODE_OFF (714)

This message causes the session, when in test mode, to return to idle state.

Example:

```
502
```

6.3.3 MACACO_REGENERATE_TRIAS (700)

It is possible at any moment for the client to request the generation of a new set of random triangles. The new set will immediately substitute the old one.

If the substitution takes place while a trial is underway, the new data will only be reported in the results file for the next trial to be started.

Two parameters must follow the command:

- The new dimensions of the box that contains the triangles (three floating-point values separated by a pipe character – |)
- The new triangle side length.

The number of triangles and their colour cannot be changed after the session has been initiated.

Example:

```
700,1184.450606|523.495321|1482.636672,11.0
```

6.3.4 MACACO_RUN_TASK (701)

Tag	Description
VSB	Vestibular task (only the platform moves)
VSL	Visual task (only the triangles move)
CMB	Combined task (both the platform and the triangles move)

Table 6.1: “Macaco” task types

When in idle mode, at the reception of this message the session will perform one standard task, as specified by the message parameters.

Seven parameters must follow the command:

- A string identifying the name of the task. This string is intended as an aid to the designer of the experiment. It won't be used by the server, but it will be included in the post-produced session result files.
- The tag identifying the task type (see Table 6.1).
- The length of the displacement in mm.
- The yaw angle (deviation from the front of the platform) in radians.
- The proportion of triangles that will move in a random direction, instead of with the requested trajectory (a floating-point number: 0.0 indicates that all triangles adopt the requested trajectory; 1.0 indicates that all triangles move in a random way).
- The maximum distance in mm. to be used along any of the three cartesian axes to assign random motions. *Random-moving triangles will each be assigned a travel vector whose three orthogonal components' absolute magnitude is at most this value.*
- The duration of the displacement in seconds.

Example:

```
701,VSB_0,VSB,282.481137,-0.153143,0.798605,328.762363,4.356646
```

6.3.5 MACACO_RUN_TASK_RING (715)

When in idle mode, at the reception of this message the session will perform one *ring* task, as specified by the message parameters.

Nine parameters must follow the command. The first seven have the same meaning as with the command to start a standard task (see Sect. 6.3.4). The two added parameters are:

- The angle on the ring device where the indicator will be positioned at the *start* of the task, in radians.
- The angle on the ring device where the indicator will be positioned at the *end* of the task, in radians.

Important tip: These angles represent an angular offset from the 12-o'clock position. Negative is counter-clockwise, while positive is clockwise.

No limit is imposed. If the absolute distance between the start and end position is $> 2\pi$, the indicator will perform more than one complete revolution during the task.

The angle that is chosen by the subject at the end of the task also represents a rotational offset. It may have been obtained by rotating anti-clockwise (and in this case you will receive a negative offset) or clockwise (resulting in a positive result). The subject may also cause the indicator to rotate more than one revolution.

It is up to the researcher to match the angles it passes and the angles it receives.

Example:

```
715, VSB_0, VSB, 304.904298, -0.151219, 0.659443, 182.335855, 2.908139, -2.413474, 2.687244
```

6.3.6 MACACO_ABORT_TASK (702)

When the server receives this message, it forces the immediate interruption of the current task, if there is one.

This implies the command to the Moog platform to return to the start position, ready for the next task.

The operation does **not** imply a freeze or abort of the platform motion.

Example:

```
702
```

6.3.7 MACACO_BEGIN_CAPTURE (711)

While a “macaco” session is underway, it is possible to capture whatever is being displayed to the right eye of the subject wearing the AR visor to a file on disk. Whenever this command is received, if movie capture is not already taking place, a new file will be opened under the session data directory, with name

```
capt.milliseconds-since-session-start.mp4
```

Example:

```
711
```

6.3.8 MACACO_END_CAPTURE (712)

If a screen capture had been previously requested by sending message MACACO_BEGIN_CAPTURE, the capture will be terminated when receiving this message, and the movie file will be properly terminated.

Example:

```
712
```

6.3.9 MACACO_GET_IPD (706)

While a “macaco” session is underway, the remote server is requested to return the current value of interpupillary distance used by the head-mounted display. The value will be returned with a subsequent MACACO_IPD_VAL message (see Sec. 6.4.5).

Example:

```
706
```

6.3.10 MACACO_SET_IPD (707)

While a “macaco” session is underway, the remote server is requested to adopt the passed value as interpupillary distance for the head-mounted display.

ONE parameter has to be specified:

- The new interpupillary distance in millimetres.

Example:

```
707,120.01023
```

6.3.11 MACACO_PARK (709)

When the client has completed the required tasks, before logging out from the server, it must send to the server this command *instead of using the generic park command*.

First, the platform will be brought back from the task start position to a position at the center of the platform space. Then, the parking procedure will proceed as usual, and the client will have to wait for a regular PARK_DONE message before the logout request can be sent.

Example:

```
709
```

6.4 Server-to-client messages

6.4.1 MACACO_ENGAGED (710)

The server informs that the preliminary phase of engagement/positioning has been completed. After this message has been received, the client may send task requests.

Example:

```
12345,710
```

6.4.2 MACACO_TASK_ACK (703)

The server informs that a task has been accepted and has been scheduled for execution. The message includes the task name as parameter.

Example:

```
12345,703,VSL_1
```

6.4.3 MACACO_TASK_NAK (704)

The execution of a task that has been requested is being refused. This may happen because the Moog platform is not engaged, because the server is not in idle state, or because the parameters could not be validated.

The message is also sent if a MACACO_PARK message is received but the server is not in idle state.

Example:

```
12345,704,"Moog not engaged"
```

6.4.4 MACACO_TASK_COMPLETED (705)

The server informs that the execution of a task has been completed.

The contents of the message are different according to the operative mode.

Standard mode

The message includes three to four parameters:

- The task name
- The time delay in milliseconds between the beginning of the task and the moment when the subject chose a direction (left/right).
- a **l** if the left choice was made, or a **r** if the right choice was made.
- If the choice was made after the forward motion had been completed, a fourth parameter will be included - a **1** (number one).

Example:

```
12345,705,VSL_1,708,r,1
```

Ring mode

The message includes four parameters:

- The task name
- The time delay in milliseconds between the beginning of the task and the moment when the subject completed the evaluation.
- a **l** if the left choice was made, or a **r** if the right choice was made.
- The chosen indicator angle in radians.

Important tip: As mentioned in the discussion about the ring task submission command (see Sect. 6.3.5), it is important to note that it is up to the researcher to match the rotation submitted by the subject and the rotation range specified when submitting the task. The subject may reach the same angle by rotating counter-clockwise (and you will thus receive a negative number) or clockwise (giving you a positive number).

Example:

```
94281,705,VSB_0,23342,1,2.512097333333334
```

6.4.5 MACACO_IPD_VAL (708)

While a “macaco” session is underway, the remote server returns, upon request, the current value of interpupillary distance used by the head-mounted display.

The message includes one parameter:

- The interpupillary distance in millimetres.

Example:

```
12345,708,120.3454
```

6.5 Session example

This commented example shows what conversation has to take place if one has to run a “macaco” session. As in the previous cases, a *red* tab indicates a message from client to server, and a *green* tab indicates a message from server to client.

```
0,6,47476,VIVE,1000.0|1000.0|500.0,1000,10.0,85a32b,0.0|0.0|250.0,2.0|40.0|-1000.0|031025,65.0
```

In the login request, type **6** indicates a “macaco” run. The parameters are described in Sec. 6.2.

```
306,1,200221.115854
```

Opening is acknowledged. The session has begun on February, 21th, at 11:58:54.

```
12815,710
```

In about 13 seconds, the engagement and positioning of the platform is confirmed with the ad-hoc message MSG_MACACO_ENGAGED. **It was not necessary to explicitly request the engagement.** This session type requires the Moog platform to be engaged all the time, thus the relative request is automatically generated by the server.

```
701, VSB_0, VSB, 373.743834, 0.178915, 0.880816, 50.546587, 3.198591
```

The client requests to initiate a *vestibular* task.

```
17152,703,VSB_0
```

The server has validated the task parameters and has begun to execute the task.

```
24079,705,VSB_0,355,1
```

The server communicates that the task has been successfully completed. The left choice has been taken 355 milliseconds after the start of the task.

```
Any number of tasks can be run at this point.
```

```
709
```

Eventually, the client requests that the Moog platform initiate a parking sequence, *by using the specific MACACO_PARK command*.

54023,10

The server communicates that the parking process has been completed (PARK_DONE).

11,100,carlo.prelz@humdek.unibe.ch,matthias.ertl@psy.unibe.ch

The client requests to close the session (message LOGOUT). Two users will receive messages with post-production results, that will be generated with a 100 millisecond step.

54680,12

The server confirms with a LOGOUT_ACK message before definitively closing the session.

Appendices

Appendix A

Topics

The concept of *topic* has been brought within the Moog platform controlling software when the number of independent research projects running in parallel started to become large.

It is obvious that an effort has to be made to ensure that each project can run for the complete duration of its data collection phase within an unchanged ecosystem.

When the first research projects that required ad-hoc code were set up (**Effe**, see Ch. 5, and **Macaco**, see Ch. 6), it was natural to create separate **GIT** branches for them. A simple system was written to allow researchers to switch between so-called *master* mode - for projects that would require plain motion sequences, and specific modes for the two ad-hoc projects.

Multiple research projects were created that made use of standard sequence-generating calls. These projects ended up using the same set of binaries and scripts. Changes for one project ended up being included in the code base used for the others - since they used the same **GIT** branch.

I decided to try and set up a system that would allow the coexistence of multiple projects in a more foolproof way. These were my goals:

- One disk directory was to include all components (scripts and binaries) for each research project.
- More than one project had to be possible, sharing the same **GIT** branch.
- A simple mechanism had to exist, similar to the pre-existing script, that would allow researchers to quickly switch between the various projects.
- All projects would have to share the same data and log repository areas, and would be reachable through the same protocol and via the same network ports.
- It would be possible to independently enable access to the various projects in emulation mode, or directly talking to the platform.

In order to distinguish the concept of these various coexisting entities from the default *branch* concept, which comes from the **GIT** world, I called these new entities **Topics**.

A.1 The procedure

I coded scripts to make much of the management of these **topics** easy. Some of the steps have to be made by hand. Here is a tentative list of the steps that have to be performed to obtain a fully defined **topic** to work with.

A.1.1 The christening

A name has to be selected for the new topic. The name ought to be short, easy to remember, and it should clearly identify the research project from those that already exist.

For the scope of the examples proposed in these pages, I propose to use `barattolo` as a name.

A.1.2 The GIT repository branches

Two repositories may happen to diverge among the various moog projects:

- The main moog code repository (http://phhum-a209-cp.unibe.ch:10012/M00/M00_Standalone)
- The repository with OpenGL code (<http://phhum-a209-cp.unibe.ch:10012/OpenGL/OpenGL-engine>)

It is expected that all research projects that make use of the Moog platform be assigned their own **GIT** branch. Maintenance becomes more complex, but one is assured that no patches are applied to production code that may modify its behaviour.

Three other repositories contain Ruby, and especially C code that is used in the Moog project. They are:

- The repository with code about reading and processing data from **HTC Vive** virtual reality visors (<http://phhum-a209-cp.unibe.ch:10012/M00/M00-lighthouse-experimental>).
- A repository that aims to be a container of generic Ruby/C material. It currently contains only some code to manage C memory blocks under Ruby, but I plan to move here at least all maths code and those routines I have written to manage time (<http://phhum-a209-cp.unibe.ch:10012/RBY/RBY-C-utils>).
- The repository that contains the code for the C library that offers an interface to the Moog platform control protocol, plus some outdated Julia glue code, and Ruby test scripts plus a C extension to connect those scripts with the platform interface library (<http://phhum-a209-cp.unibe.ch:10012/M00/M00-c-interface>).

```
1 export MOO_USER=moog
   export MOO_HOME=/home/${MOO_USER}/
```

Listing A.1: System variables for the *topic* subsystem.

Each *topic* will reside in a subdirectory of a master directory whose name is composed as follows:

- The content of system variable `MOO_HOME`. This variable has to be defined in the system's `/etc/profile` file. See for example the contents of Listing A.1. If the variable is not defined, hardcoded string `/home/moog/` will be used.
- The string `b/`
- The name of the *topic*.

A.2 Environments

Topics are *local to the machine they are created on*. Their availability may be further limited to zero or more existing **environments**. This concept is brought into the picture of *topics* in order to permit the coexistence of runs making use of the platform emulator, and runs where the actual Moog platform is controlled.

There is a theoretical possibility to extend the list of available environments when new possibilities are created.

Important tip: Each *topic* can be associated to any of the environment, or to none at all. This option gives the possibility to concretely black out a *topic* that is not in use anymore. It is sufficient not to associate it to any environment.

A.3 The management tool

I wrote a tool with a simple GUI to permit the completion of two tasks:

- The creation of new *topics*.
- The association of the existing topics to various environments.

In order to make use of this tool, you must be either running on the screen of the actual PC where the topic will reside, or be connected to it from another machine running Xwindows, with a fast ethernet link to the operative PC. Go to any recent, operative checkout of the M00_standalone repository, and type:

```
ruby scripts/topic_mgmt.rb
```

A.3.1 *Topic* creation

By selecting the first tab on top of the application window, you access the *topic* creation screen.

Figure A.1: *Topic* creation screen

These information will have to be provided in order to create a new topic:

- A unique name (just letters, digits and underscores) to identify the topic
- A brief description, that will appear on the background screen when the topic has been selected (see [Img. A.2](#)).
- The path to an image that will also appear on the background screen. The image ought to provide to the researcher, together with the short description, a visual confirmation that the right *topic* is currently selected on the running machine.
- The branches to choose for both the main and the OpenGL code repositories.
- The choice of which environments the new *topic* will be active for.

Important tip: At least one environment has to be selected for a new *topic* when creating it. Only later will it be possible to disable all environments, and thus virtually disable the *topic*.

Fig. A.1 shows what the *topic* creation script looks like when all parameters have been provided, the **Validate** button has been pressed, and the parameter validation process has been successfully concluded. If some error had been detected, you would have been presented with an explanatory window, and the coloured square at the bottom center would not have changed from red to green.

As soon as the validation phase has been passed, the **Proceed** button becomes clickable. If you do so, the creation process begins, some informative messages are shown, and at the end of the creation process the tool window will close, leaving you to the text terminal from where you had started the utility.

The text you will find on your screen are similar to the following:

```
scripts/topic_mgmt.rb:596:in `exit': exit
from scripts/topic_mgmt.rb:596:in `proceed'
from scripts/topic_mgmt.rb:140:in `block in initialize'
from /usr/local/lib/ruby/gems/2.8.0/gems/gobject-introspection-3.4.1/lib/gobject-introspection/loader.rb:600:in `invoke'
from /usr/local/lib/ruby/gems/2.8.0/gems/gobject-introspection-3.4.1/lib/gobject-introspection/loader.rb:600:in `invoke'
from /usr/local/lib/ruby/gems/2.8.0/gems/gobject-introspection-3.4.1/lib/gobject-introspection/loader.rb:514:in `block in
↳ define_method'
from scripts/topic_mgmt.rb:623:in `<main>'
```

This resembles an error message, but if the word **exit** can be read at the end of the first line, this means that the utility concluded its run with success.

Important tip: This tool is not to be used often, and I could not test it extensively. I removed all bugs that manifested themselves, but it should still be considered *beta*-level code. If errors are shown or if the tool appears to be frozen, please inform me with details (screenshots, if possible). The topic database can be fixed by hand, but the process is too experimental to be described in these notes.

At this point you will find the collected and generated data for this new *topic* in its own directory. In the case of the present example:

```
/home/moog/b/barattolo/
```


Figure A.2: *Topic* background screen

A.3.2 Environment toggling

By selecting the second tab on top of the application window, you access the *topic* environment toggling screen.

Figure A.3: *Topic* environment toggling screen

You can sort the list of available *topics* by alphabetical order, by creation date or by modification date by double-clicking the header of the relative column in the display. If you change any of the environment validity checkboxes, you then have to press button **Validate** to save the changes. This will also make you leave the application. Otherwise, to leave the application without changing anything, you can always bring into focus the text screen from which you fired the application and type **Ctrl-C**.

A.4 The selection tool

The selection tool can be accessed by anyone having access to the main screen of the Moog PC. By clicking the middle button of the mouse, a small menu will appear. Choose item **Change topic** from it, and the window shown in Fig. A.4 will be shown.

Figure A.4: *Topic* selection screen

By checking or unchecking box **Emulated**, the list of topics to select will change, allowing you to select those *topics* which are available for emulation run, or for run on the actual platform. Choose the desired *topic* and click the **Confirm** button, and the graphical system of the machine will be restarted based on the requested *topic*, with the platform emulation running if needed.

Appendix B

Backups

When the development of topics (see [A](#)) has become available, it has become possible to develop a distributed backup mechanism that could follow these guidelines:

- As many copies of backed-up data as desired.
- Back-up data contained in simple USB-connected memory devices.
- Devices containing back-ups for one or more existing topic.
- Saving of:
 - The topic bulk data including code and binaries, saved in a GIT repository, with modifications along time.
 - Data of the sessions that were run for the given topic.
 - Log files referring to the given topic.
- Procedures of partition creation and association of topics to partitions requiring superuser rights.
- Procedure of partition update automatically started by inserting the specific device in a USB port of the moog server, with a simple GUI device appearing on-screen, that it is up to the researcher to interact with, and eventually close *before disconnecting the device*.

B.1 Partition creation

Partition creation has to be executed as root. Make use of any removable device that has free space (i.e. *disk space not assigned to any partition*.)

Whether you start with a new device or you recycle an old device that had been used for other purposes, **you first have to remove existing partitions until enough free space is available on-disk.**

You can make use of text-base utility **fdisk**, of GUI app **gparted**, or of any other partitioning utility you are confident with.

Important tip: The usage of *any* partitioning utility is intrinsically dangerous. You run the risk of deleting whole existing partitions on any disk. Damages of this sort are usually *not recoverable*.

Here follows a brief example using **gparted**.

Plug in your disk

By analyzing the system log files, you will find out which device your disk is assigned to For example, from this output:

```

[2972167.518249] usb 4-1: new SuperSpeed Gen 1 USB device number 22 using xhci_hcd
[2972167.539972] usb 4-1: New USB device found, idVendor=0bc2, idProduct=231a, bcdDevice= 7.10
[2972167.539973] usb 4-1: New USB device strings: Mfr=1, Product=2, SerialNumber=3
[2972167.539973] usb 4-1: Product: Expansion
[2972167.539974] usb 4-1: Manufacturer: Seagate
[2972167.539974] usb 4-1: SerialNumber: NAASNP5M
[2972167.548150] scsi host6: uas
[2972167.548551] scsi 6:0:0:0: Direct-Access      Seagate  Expansion          0710 PQ: 0 ANSI: 6
[2972167.549325] scsi 6:0:0:0: Attached scsi generic sg2 type 0
[2972171.244558] sd 6:0:0:0: [sdc] 1953525167 512-byte logical blocks: (1.00 TB/932 GiB)
[2972171.244559] sd 6:0:0:0: [sdc] 4096-byte physical blocks
[2972171.244760] sd 6:0:0:0: [sdc] Write Protect is off
[2972171.244761] sd 6:0:0:0: [sdc] Mode Sense: 53 00 00 08
[2972171.245005] sd 6:0:0:0: [sdc] Write cache: enabled, read cache: enabled, doesn't support DPO or
↪ FUA
[2972171.245299] sd 6:0:0:0: [sdc] Optimal transfer size 33553920 bytes not a multiple of physical
↪ block size (4096 bytes)
[2972171.540360] sdc: sdc1 sdc2 sdc3 < sdc5 sdc6 sdc7 >
[2972171.580339] sd 6:0:0:0: [sdc] Attached SCSI disk
[2972172.580534] EXT4-fs (sdc6): mounted filesystem with ordered data mode. Opts: (null)

```

you can desume that your device is assigned to `/hili/dev/sdc`.

Run `gparted`

Fig. B.1 shows an example screen after opening the partitioning tool and selecting the right disk.

Figure B.1: `Gparted`: disk situation

As you can notice, my device is a **1TB** device with almost 733GB of unallocated space in its logical partition.

Create a new partition

By clicking on the available space with the right-hand mouse button, I am able to ask for the creation of a new partition making use of some of that space. Fig. B.2 shows the screen of the partition-creation screen, once the proper data have been inserted.

I have requested my partition to occupy **300.000 MiB**, or about 300 GB.

Figure B.2: **Gparted**: partition creation

Important tip: The most important element in the screen is the selection of the **File system**. As default, this field will come pre-selected to **ext4**. You must select option **unformatted**, as shown in the image.

Confirm the creation. Eventually, the screen will look similar to Fig. B.3.

Figure B.3: **Gparted**: the partition has been created

Be sure to note the partition name. In our case, it is `/dev/sdc7`.

Run the backup partition creation utility itself

Now you can run the backup partition creation utility. As `root`, change your working directory to

```
/home/moog/b/master
```

and execute the following command

```
ruby -I ./libs scripts/backup_creator.rb name partition
```

where:

- *name* is the name you want to give to this backup partition¹.

¹You can only use letters, numbers and underscores. Be sure to give meaningful names to your backup partitions!

- *partition* is the partition name you previously marked down.

For example:

```
ruby -I ./libs scripts/backup_creator.rb test_part_for_doc /dev/sdc7
```

Be sure to confirm the request. Here is an example output of this command:

```
[201110.110114] /dev/sdc7 (for test_part_for_doc) has 76800000 blocks
About to create PLACO backup partition [test_part_for_doc] on device /dev/sdc7.
Are you REALLY sure?
type YES to confirm: YES
[201110.110144] Executing <mkfs.ext4 -b 4096 -L PLACO_test_part_for_doc /dev/sdc7 76799999>
Warning: label too long; will be truncated to 'PLACO_test_part_'

mke2fs 1.45.6 (20-Mar-2020)
Creating filesystem with 76799999 4k blocks and 19202048 inodes
Filesystem UUID: 145edc4d-0eb1-4b9b-a131-ebef28548213
Superblock backups stored on blocks:
    32768, 98304, 163840, 229376, 294912, 819200, 884736, 1605632, 2654208,
    4096000, 7962624, 11239424, 20480000, 23887872, 71663616

    Allocating group tables: done
    Writing inode tables: done
    Creating journal (262144 blocks): done
    Writing superblocks and filesystem accounting information: done

[201110.110156] PLACO backup partition [test_part_for_doc] created under /dev/sdc7.
```

B.2 Partition signature removal

The backup partition is marked with a specific signature to identify it as PLACO backup, and to make sure that you do not accidentally overwrite it by running this command once again.

A utility is provided to remove the signature in case this is needed. You run it as follows: As *root*, change your working directory to

```
/home/moog/b/master
```

and execute the following command

```
ruby -I ./libs scripts/backup_del_signature.rb partition
```

where *partition* is the disk. device Be sure you *really* want to remove a partition signature before you run this command.

B.3 Adding a topic to a Partition

Backup partitions can collect back-ups for more than one topic. After creation, a partition is not associated with any topic. You can make an association by running a specific utility.

As *root*, change your working directory to

```
/home/moog/b/master
```

and execute the following command

```
ruby -I ./libs scripts/backup_add_topic.rb partition
```

You will be presented with an output similar to this one:

```
[201110.111249] Mounted PLACO bkup part [test_part_for_doc] from /dev/sdc7. Has 0 topics.  
  
PLACO partition [test_part_for_doc]  
  
System topics that may be added:  
 1) barattolo  
 2) effe2  
 3) master  
Select topic (return=abort):
```

Select the number correspondent with the topic you want to associate to your partition. E.g. **3**, correspondent to topic *master*.

At the end of the run, your backup partition will be initialized to back up the chosen topic.

Important tip: You can back up more than one topic in your partition. It is sufficient to repeat the steps above for each topic you want the partition to store the back-up of.

B.4 Backup data collection

Backup data collection is supposed to be a routine operation, quick and as easy as possible.

What you need to do is plug the device into one of the USB3 sockets at the rear of the Moog machine.

Important tip: You can plug in your device at any moment, but it is obviously suggested to do that when the machine is idle, i.e. when no data collection session is underway.

Soon after the pen has been connected, a GUI window similar to the one shown in Fig. B.4a.

The window will contain reference for **all** the PLACO backup partitions present in the device. In the example you can see the partition that we have just created, called *test_part_for_doc*, but above it you can see details for another partition, called *Zli_zlo*, which does hold backups for **four** topics.

Important tip: You can choose to update the back-up for any of the topics, in any order, or for none at all.

You request the back-up update to take place by pressing the button labeled **Back up**, that you can find on the side of the topic details.

Fig. B.4b shows what the screen may look like after a backup has been updated. As you can see, the space near the bottom of the screen displays system messages generated while the backup process is being performed.

Whenever all the topic backups you wished to perform have been completed, just press the button named *Close*, and the backup process will cleanly complete.

(a) Ready for backup

(b) Backup completed

Figure B.4: Backup process

Important tip: It is safe to remove the device from the Moog PC **only after the GUI screen has cleanly completed**. Please do not remove the device before closing the screen. Please do not kill the GUI window in any other way than by pressing the *Close* button.

B.5 Backup data access

Backup data is stored within a Linux *Ext4* partition. You can easily mount it on another Linux Machine, and there also exist ways to mount *Ext4* partitions under windows. See for example <https://www.howtogeek.com/112888/3-ways-to-access-your-linux-partitions-from-windows/>.

In order to avoid the risk of damaging the backup data, I invite you to always mount the partition **read-only**.

Here is a brief description about what you can find in the partition.

B.5.1 The *bklog* file

The *bklog* file is a simple text file where informations are added whenever the partition is accessed.

Here is an example excerpt:

```
[201110.110156] Created
[201110.111007] Mounted
[201110.111007] Begin backup session
[201110.111031] End backup session
[201110.111031] Unmounted
[201110.111249] Mounted
```

```
[201110.111505] Unmounted
[201110.124034] Mounted
[201110.124049] Added topic master
[201110.124049] Unmounted
[201110.125417] Mounted
[201110.125417] Begin backup session
[201110.125500] End backup session
[201110.125500] Unmounted
...
...
```

B.5.2 Topic directories

All other backed-up data refer to selected topics. Data for one topic are included in a directory called

```
topics/topic-name
```

B.5.3 Per-topic: GIT repository

Directories

```
topics/topic-name/topic_repo
```

and

```
topics/topic-name/topic_git
```

contain a GIT repository of the topic area that can be found on the Moog server at the moment when backup takes place.

Every time backup is ran, the whole directory is copied (with `rsync`) to this area, and then a new commit is made.

Important tip: The GIT versioning information of the various repositories that compose the topic material is **not** saved in the backup repository. The reason for this repository is to have a trace of the actual files (scripts, binary libraries) that were used to make the various runs. Of course, the granularity of this information depends on how often the backup process is ran.

Under Linux, in order to access the versioning information, e.g. by using a program like `gitk`, you have to proceed as follows:

1. Mount the backup partition on your machine. Let's say that your mount point is `/mnt`.
2. Say you want to access git repo for topic `master`. You need to assign environment variable `GIT_DIR` to the location of the `topic_git` directory:

```
export GIT_DIR=/mnt/topics/master/topic_git
```

3. You will change directory to the `topic_repo` directory:

```
cd /mnt/topics/master/topic_repo
```

4. At this point you can run any GIT command, including `gitk`.

B.5.4 Per-topic: session data

Directory

```
topics/topic-name/topic_data
```

contains a copy of data produced for all sessions ran for the given topic. The directory structure is (a subsection of) the structure to be found under `/moog_base/sessions/` on the Moog server.

This includes all post-production data archives.

Important tip: If you happen to request new post-production runs (e.g. with a new millisecond sample rate for the motion data), the new material will be synchronised to any backup partition at the next backup run.

B.5.5 Per-topic: run logs

Directory

```
topics/topic-name/topic_logs
```

will contain a copy of all the *master* log files generated for sessions that were started for the given topic. This material will mostly be used (rarely) for debug or anecdotal evidence.